
EQUILIBRIUM MEASURES FOR
NONLOCAL AND ANISOTROPIC
LOGARITHMIC ENERGIES

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Contents

Introduction	vii
1 Preliminaries & Notation	1
1.1 Lower Semicontinuity	1
1.2 A Short Introduction to Γ -convergence	4
1.2.1 Examples	7
1.3 Some Measure Theory	9
1.3.1 Weak Convergence of Measures	9
1.3.2 Push-forward of Measures	11
1.4 Primer on the Fourier Transform	12
2 Classical Case of Logarithmic Interactions	15
2.1 The Mean-Field Energy	15
2.1.1 Γ -convergence to the Mean Field Energy	17
2.2 Minimisation of the Mean Field Energy	25
2.2.1 Alternative Proof of Strict Convexity of Interaction Energy	28
2.2.2 The Euler-Lagrange Conditions	31
2.2.3 Characterisation of the Minimiser of I	35
2.3 Scaled Confinement Potential	37
3 Anisotropic Energies	39
3.1 Anisotropic Confinement Potential	39
3.2 Anisotropic Interaction Potential	44
3.2.1 Limit Case: $\alpha = 1$	52
3.3 Numerics	53
3.3.1 $W(x) = -\log x + \alpha \left(\frac{x_1^2}{ x ^2}\right)^p$ and $V(x) = x ^2$ with $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}, p \geq 2$	54
3.3.2 $W(x) = -\log x $ and $V(x) = \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2$	57
3.3.3 $W(x) = -\log x $ and $V(x) = x ^p$ with $p \geq 2$	58
3.3.4 $W(x) = -\log x + \alpha \frac{x_1^2}{ x ^2}$ and $V(x) = \beta x_1^2 + \gamma x_2^2$, with $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}$	58
3.3.5 $W(x) = -\log x + \alpha \frac{x_1^2}{ x ^2}$ and $V(x) = x ^p$	59
A Chapter 1	61
B Chapter 2	63
Bibliography	65

Introduction

Nonlocal energy functionals of the form

$$I(\mu) = \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\mu(x), \quad (1)$$

where μ denotes a probability measure on \mathbb{R}^2 , arise naturally in various different contexts, covering a range of disciplines. In the physical, biological and material sciences, interaction energies such as I are typically used to model the behaviour of large collections of particles and the effects the particles have on each other via pairwise interactions. These models are typically used to explain fundamental collective behaviour that particles take under certain constraints and situations, e.g. when studying a cloud of electrons, a flock of birds, a school of fish, a crowd of people, defects in materials or vortices in superconductors [28, 8, 7, 9, 22, 23, 6, 14, 29, 26, 25]. In these examples, the interaction energy I describes the average, or *mean field*, behaviour of the system, since it is the continuum approximation of the real world discrete system given by

$$I_n(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n W(x_i - x_j) + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V(x_i), \quad (2)$$

where $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^2$ denote the positions of particles in the plane, and the precise nature of W and V are dependent on the particle system. In this thesis the function $W : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ describes a repulsive interaction potential between any two particles with a critical singularity at zero, which prohibits the particles from occupying the same space, and $V : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ describes an attractive confinement potential which makes sure that the particles remain within a bounded region. These types of interaction are called *attractive-repulsive* interactions. The functional I is deemed *nonlocal* since the behaviour of the integrand $W * \mu(y)$ at any point $y \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is dependent on the behaviour of W and μ at any other point on the domain, not just a local neighbourhood of y .

In nature, it is commonly observed that large numbers of particles self-assemble in such a way to minimise their total interaction energy I . For example, a cloud of electrons, known as a Coulomb gas, under the influence of an external magnetic field arranges in such a way to minimise its total repulsion energy. Obviously, in a system consisting of two electrons under the influence of an isotropic external magnetic field acting in such a way to confine the electrons to a bounded domain, the distribution of the electrons take to minimise their total interaction energy is a straight line. In a system consisting of three electrons, the minimising distribution is achieved when the electrons are distributed in an equilateral triangle, and in a system consisting of 4, a square. As the number of electrons in the system increases, the problem of determining what distribution the electrons take quickly gets very challenging, since such a calculation becomes very computationally heavy. In general, for n electrons located at $x_1, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^2$, their discrete interaction energy is given by the Hamiltonian I_n in (2), where W now represents the Coulomb interaction potential, i.e. $W = -\log|\cdot|$ and V a magnetic potential. As n gets very large, the discrete energy, I_n of this Coulomb gas, can be well approximated by its continuum model $I(\mu)$ in (1), where μ represents the distribution of the electrons in \mathbb{R}^2 . The way the discrete

Figure 1: Examples of particle systems that are of interest. (a) A flock of birds, (b) A school of fish.

energy I_n and the continuum energy I are related is subtle. If we just had that I_n converges to I pointwise, then the minimisers of I_n and I would not be related. Instead, we make use Γ -convergence, a tool developed by Ennio De Giorgi, which is widely used in the modern theory of the calculus of variations [13]. Ennio De Giorgi's pioneering work in the calculus of variations paved the way for its modern theory and allowed for further developments in the field. We use Γ -convergence because it has the very useful properties of preserving minimisers. This is quite useful when wanting to determine minimisers of large particle systems, since the minimisers of the Γ -limit, i.e. the continuum approximation I , well approximates the minimisers of I_n . Hence the minimiser of I , called the *equilibrium measure*, is a good approximation of the minimiser of I_n for large n . This is the object that we are going to characterise.

Natural questions that arise in the study of distributions of large particles systems are: what is the distribution the particles take, in particular what properties does this distribution possess, i.e. what are its symmetry properties, what is the dimension of the support (are the particles distributed in a line, or spread out), is the mass distributed uniformly? Many of these questions are left unanswered when considering general interactions, and the relationship between the potentials W, V , and these properties of the equilibrium measure, is currently not fully understood. Although, it has recently been determined that the dimension of the support of the equilibrium measure is intimately related to the strength of the singularity present in the interaction potential [4].

The problem of studying equilibrium measures of interaction energies such as I has very classical roots, and the case of purely logarithmic interactions, $W = -\log|\cdot|$ under various confinement terms has been studied extensively over the last century, in several different contexts, including Fekete sets, Random Matrices, Ginzburg-Landau vortices and orthogonal polynomials, see [18, 2, 19, 21, 29, 26, 25, 30] and references therein. The classical case of $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$ was solved by Frostman in his 1935 seminal paper [16], where he deduced that the equilibrium measure can be explicitly represented as the characteristic measure on the unit disc, i.e. $\mu_0 = \frac{1}{\pi}\chi_{B_1(0)}$. That is under logarithmic interaction and a quadratic confinement potential, to minimise their interaction energy, particles evenly distribute themselves over a unit disc.

Typically, current interaction models only consider isotropic interaction and confinement potentials, but in the real world, many interactions tend to be anisotropic. For example in the case of a large crowd of people, pairwise interactions not only tend to depend on the distance between two individuals, but also each individual's field of view, i.e. interactions have angular

dependence, deeming them anisotropic. There has been recent developments in the study of anisotropic interaction energies in material science, where certain anisotropic interaction energies describe defects in the atomic structure of metals, called *dislocations*, which at macroscopic scales determine the way that metal deforms [17, 22, 9, 23]. Moreover, anisotropic interaction energies has recently been studied in connection with pattern formation in the development of fingerprints [6], which has clear applications to forensic science, and also in connection with aggregation models in biological applications [14].

The aim of this thesis is to study the minimisers of interaction energies of the form (1), where μ is a probability measure on \mathbb{R}^2 , W is a repulsive interaction potential with a very critical logarithmic singularity at zero and V is an attractive *confinement* potential, which works against W and makes sure that the minimising measures have compact support on \mathbb{R}^2 (i.e. V grows faster than W at infinity). In particular, we are interested in determining the properties of minimisers of the interaction energy I under various different potentials W and V , both isotropic and anisotropic. We aim to study the classical logarithmic potential in detail and determine the equilibrium measure explicitly through Frostman-type methods [16, 24]. Furthermore, we want to understand the effect an anisotropy has on the equilibrium measure when it is introduced in the interaction potential and the confinement potential, e.g. the effect on the dimension of the support, the distribution of mass and the symmetries of the equilibrium measure.

This thesis is organised as follows: in Chapter 1, we cover some of the preliminaries required throughout the report, including a short introduction to Γ -convergence, some important results from measure theory and from Fourier analysis. In Chapter 2, we study the classical problem of the radially symmetric logarithmic interaction potential with a quadratic confinement potential, [16], by proving existence and uniqueness of minimisers and then concluding with the calculation of the unique equilibrium measure explicitly. In Chapter 3, we proceed to study a less classical problem by introducing anisotropies to both the interaction and confinement potential, by computing explicitly the equilibrium measures in both cases. We conclude the chapter by carrying out numerical simulations for discrete interaction energies, for large numbers of particles, with various different interaction and confinement potentials. In particular, we plot the distribution the particles take with the use of MATLAB, and check that the the continuum model provides a good approximation of the minimising distribution.

Further Work: There are many directions in which one could take this research into. Currently, equilibrium measures for nonlocal interaction energies have been computed explicitly for a limited number of cases, therefore is large demand to understand the properties of equilibrium measures for more general interaction and confinement potentials. To tackle this, a pure analytic approach could be taken to further understand the sufficient and necessary conditions on these potentials for equilibrium measures to have certain properties, e.g. fully dimensional support or certain symmetries.

It would also be interesting to determine the behaviour of the equilibrium measure in the absence of a confinement potential but under probability measures which are supported on a given set $S \subset \mathbb{R}^2$. This has recently been touched on through the analysis of the obstacle problem [3]. In this scenario, it is widely understood that under purely logarithmic interactions, the equilibrium measure would have support on the boundary of the set, ∂S . It would be interesting to see whether anisotropies of the form W_α introduced in Chapter 3 would still lead to vertical wall structures as in the case with the presence of a confinement potential field.

Chapter 1

Preliminaries & Notation

NOTATION

$\mathcal{M}(A)$	Set of signed measures with support contained in A .
$\mathcal{M}^+(A)$	Set of measures with support contained in A .
$\text{supp}\mu$	The support of a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}$, see Definition 1.36.
$\mathcal{P}(A)$	Set of Borel probability measures on A .
\wedge, \vee	$a \wedge b = \min\{a, b\}$ and $a \vee b = \max\{a, b\}$.
Δ	The diagonal entries of $\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2$, namely $\Delta := \{(x, x) \mid x \in \mathbb{R}^2\}$.
\lfloor	Measure restriction, i.e. $\mu \lfloor E = 1_E \cdot \mu$.
$\text{cap}_{\mathcal{W}}$	The capacity of a set with respect to a given potential \mathcal{W} , see Definition 2.11.
$C_b(X)$	The space of all bounded continuous functions $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.
$C_c(X)$	The space of all continuous functions $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with compact support.
$C^r(X)$	The space of all continuous and r -differentiable functions $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with continuous r th derivative.
$C(X, Y)$	The space of all continuous functions $f : X \rightarrow Y$.
\mathcal{L}^d	The d -dimensional Lebesgue measure.
$\overline{\mathbb{R}}, \overline{\mathbb{C}}$	The extended real/complex spaces, i.e. $\overline{\mathbb{R}} = \mathbb{R} \cup \{\pm\infty\}$ and $\overline{\mathbb{C}} = \mathbb{C} \cup \{\pm\infty \pm i\infty\}$.
\mathbb{N}_0	$\mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$.
$\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{S}'$	The Schwarz space and its corresponding dual, see Definition 1.46.
$\hat{\cdot}, \check{\cdot}$	The Fourier and anti-Fourier transforms, see Definition 1.47.
$a_n \nearrow a$	Denotes the convergence of a sequence a_n to a and $a_n \leq a_{n+1}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
$\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$	Denote the weak convergence (against functions $f \in C_b$, see Definition 1.37).
$\Omega(a, b)$	Denotes the region enclosed by an ellipse of semi-axes a and b , namely the set $\left\{x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \frac{x_1^2}{a^2} + \frac{x_2^2}{b^2} < 1\right\}$.

In this chapter, we recall some results from measure theory and Fourier analysis, and give a short introduction to Γ -convergence.

1.1 Lower Semicontinuity

We begin by defining lower semicontinuity. For the following, let X denote a non-empty set, and (X, d) a metric space.

Definition 1.1 (Lower Semicontinuity)

A function $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is *lower semicontinuous at a point* $x \in X$ if for every $t \in \mathbb{R}$ with $t < f(x)$, there exists an open neighbourhood $U \subseteq X$ of x such that $t < f(y)$ for every $y \in U$. We say that f is lower semicontinuous on X if f is lower semicontinuous at each point $x \in X$. A function $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is said to be *upper semicontinuous* if $-f$ is lower semicontinuous.

Definition 1.2 (Sequential Lower Semicontinuity)

A function $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is said to be *sequentially lower semicontinuous* at a point $x \in X$ if for every sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ we have

$$x_n \xrightarrow{d} x \implies \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) \geq f(x). \quad (1.1)$$

Furthermore, f is said to be sequentially lower semicontinuous on X if it is sequentially lower semicontinuous at all $x \in X$.

Definition 1.3 (Lower Semicontinuous Envelope)

The *lower semicontinuous envelope* of a function $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{l.s.c.}(f)(x) &:= \sup\{g(x) \mid g : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}} \text{ is lower semicontinuous and } g \leq f \text{ on } X\} \\ &= \inf \left\{ \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) \mid (x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X \text{ and } x_n \xrightarrow{d} x \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.2)$$

Remark 1.4

Definition 1.1 does not require a metric space, but only a topology τ . In a general topological space, lower semicontinuity implies sequential lower semicontinuity, but the opposite is not true. Sequential lower semicontinuity implies lower semicontinuity only if the topological space (X, τ) satisfies the first axiom of countability, i.e. the neighbourhood of every point in X has a countable base. Since all metric spaces satisfy the first axiom of countability, and throughout this thesis we will be working in the space \mathbb{R}^2 under the usual metric, we shall use the terms lower semicontinuous and sequentially lower semicontinuous interchangeably.

Moreover, in Definition 1.3, the sequential definition we give for the lower semicontinuous envelope of a function only holds true in topological spaces that satisfy the first axiom of countability. For the definition of a lower semicontinuous function and lower semicontinuous envelope (or relaxed function) on a general topological space, see [12, Chapter 3].

Remark 1.5 (Properties of Lower Semicontinuous Functions)

- (i) A function $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous if and only if it is both upper and lower semicontinuous.
- (ii) It can easily be seen by the definition of sequential lower semicontinuity, if functions $f, g : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ are lower semicontinuous, then $f + g$ is also lower semicontinuous. In fact, any linear combinations of lower semicontinuous functions with non-negative coefficients is lower semicontinuous.
- (iii) Furthermore, for a sequence of lower semicontinuous functions $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, the supremum, $\sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} f_n$, is also lower semicontinuous.

Theorem 1.6

Let X be a compact and $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be sequentially lower semicontinuous. Then there exists $x_0 \in X$ such that

$$f(x_0) = \inf_{x \in X} f(x).$$

Proof. Let f be as above, and let $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a minimising sequence in X , i.e. such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = \inf_{x \in X} f(x)$. Since X is compact, the sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a convergent subsequence, say $(x_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$, that converges to some $x_0 \in X$. As f is lower semicontinuous, $\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} f(x_{n_k}) \geq f(x_0)$. Therefore, $\inf_{x \in X} f(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} f(x_{n_k}) \geq f(x_0)$. But $\inf_{x \in X} f(x) \leq f(x_0)$, which implies the result. \square

Theorem 1.7 (See [24, Theorem 0.1.1])

A function $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is lower semicontinuous on the compact set X if, and only if there exists a sequence of continuous functions $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $f_n : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $f_n \nearrow f$ pointwise increasingly as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. (\Leftarrow): Since for all $x \in X$ we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = f(x)$, it follows that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = f(x)$, and hence f is lower semicontinuous.

(\Rightarrow) Assume that f is lower semicontinuous. If $f \equiv +\infty$, then the statement follows directly. If instead $f < \infty$, define the functions $f_n : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows

$$f_n(x) := \inf_{y \in X} \{f(y) + nd(x, y)\},$$

where the infimum is attained and is finite since X is compact. Let $x \in X$, and for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $\epsilon > 0$ and $\delta = \frac{\epsilon}{n}$ such that $d(x, y) < \delta$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} |f_n(x) - f_n(y)| &= \left| \inf_{z \in X} \{f(z) + nd(x, z)\} - \inf_{z \in X} \{f(z) + nd(y, z)\} \right| \\ &\leq n \sup_{z \in X} |d(x, z) - d(y, z)| \leq nd(x, y) < \epsilon. \end{aligned}$$

Hence f_n is continuous for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. It is also easy to see that f_n is a monotonically increasing function, and that for any $x \in X$ we have $f_n(x) = \inf_{y \in X} \{f(y) + nd(x, y)\} \leq f(x)$.

We are left to prove that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = f(x)$. Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Since f is lower semicontinuous and the distance function d is continuous, the function $y \mapsto f(y) + nd(x, y)$ is lower semicontinuous and bounded from below. Then by properties of the infimum, for $\epsilon > 0$ there exists $x_n \in X$ such that $f_n(x) > f(x_n) + nd(x, x_n) - \epsilon$. Now let $\alpha = \inf_{x \in X} f(x)$. Then since $f_n(x) \leq f(x)$ for all $x \in X$, we have that

$$f(x) \geq f_n(x) \geq f(x_n) + nd(x, x_n) - \epsilon > \alpha + nd(x, x_n) - \epsilon. \quad (\star)$$

Then by (\star) we can conclude that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x, x_n) = 0$, and so by the lower semicontinuity f , it follows that

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f(x_n) + nd(x, x_n) - \epsilon) \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) - \epsilon \geq f(x) - \epsilon.$$

This holds for all $\epsilon > 0$, therefore we obtain that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \geq f(x)$. Furthermore, since $f_n(x) \leq f(x)$, for all $x \in X$ and $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, the result $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \leq f(x)$ follows immediately. Hence for all $x \in X$, we have that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = f(x)$, as required. \square

Remark 1.8

The result of Theorem 1.7 in fact also when $X = \mathbb{R}^2$. This can be proved by repeating the proof of Theorem 1.7, but instead with

$$f_n(x) := \inf_{y \in X} \{f(y) + g(|x - y|)\},$$

where $g : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is continuous, and is such that $g(0) = 0$ and g grows sufficiently fast so that the infimum in the definition of f_n is attained.

Definition 1.9 (Convexity)

Let X be a linear vector space over \mathbb{R} . A set $A \subseteq X$ is said to be *convex* if for any $x, y \in A$ and $t \in [0, 1]$, we have $(1 - t)x + ty \in A$. Furthermore, we say that a function $f : A \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$, defined on a convex set $A \subset X$, is *convex* if for all $x, y \in A$ such that $f(x), f(y) < \infty$,

$$f((1 - t)x + ty) \leq (1 - t)f(x) + tf(y) \quad \forall t \in [0, 1].$$

We say that the function f is *strictly convex* if $f \not\equiv \infty$ and for all $x, y \in A$ such that $x \neq y$, $f(x), f(y) < \infty$, we have

$$f((1 - t)x + ty) < (1 - t)f(x) + tf(y) \quad \forall t \in (0, 1).$$

Proposition 1.10

Let X be a linear vector space and let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be a strictly convex function on X . Then $\min_{x \in X} f(x)$, if it exists, is unique.

Proof. Assume that there exists $x_0 \in X$ such that $f(x_0) = \min_{x \in X} f(x) < \infty$. Let $y \in X$ be another minimiser of f on X and assume that $y \neq x_0$. Then by strict convexity of f , for $t = 1/2$

$$f\left(\frac{1}{2}(x_0 + y)\right) < \frac{1}{2}(f(x_0) + f(y)) = \min_{x \in X} f(x).$$

But this directly contradicts minimality, and hence we must have that $x_0 = y$. \square

1.2 A Short Introduction to Γ -convergence

We now introduce Γ -convergence, a convergence concept which is widely used in the modern theory of the Calculus of Variations. First, we recall some more familiar definitions of convergence. For the following, assume that X is a non-empty set, and (X, d) is a metric space.

Definition 1.11 (Pointwise Convergence)

For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$, and let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$. Then we say that f_n converges to f *pointwise* if for each $x \in X$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(f_n(x), f(x)) = 0$.

Definition 1.12 (Uniform Convergence)

For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$, and let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$. Then we say that f_n converges to f *uniformly* if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{x \in X} d(f_n(x), f(x)) = 0$.

We now give the definition of Γ -convergence of functions.

Definition 1.13 (Γ -convergence)

We say that a sequence $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of functions $f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ Γ -converges to a function $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ if the following two inequalities hold

- (i) (Γ -lim inf) For all $x \in X$ and all sequences $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x$, we have $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) \geq f(x)$.
- (ii) (Γ -lim sup) For all $x \in X$, there is a sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x$ and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) \leq f(x)$. Such a sequence is called a *recovery sequence*.

Remark 1.14

By part (i) of Definition 1.13, part (ii) may instead be written as:

- (ii)* For all $x \in X$, there is a sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) = f(x)$.

Theorem 1.15 (Uniqueness of Γ -limit)

Let $f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be a sequence of functions. Then, if it exists, the Γ -limit of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is unique.

Proof. Assume that the Γ -limit of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ exists, and let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ and $g : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ denote the Γ -limits of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. Then by Remark 1.14 and by the definition of Γ -convergence, for all $x \in X$ there exists a recovery sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x$ and $f(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) = g(x)$. Thus $f(x) = g(x)$ for all $x \in X$ and hence $f \equiv g$, which proves uniqueness of Γ -limits. \square

It should be noted that Γ -convergence is dependent on the metric on the given space X . In general, the existence of the Γ -limit in one metric does not imply the existence of the Γ -limit in another. Moreover, if we have two metrics, say d, \hat{d} such that convergence in \hat{d} implies convergence in d , then if the Γ -limits of a sequence $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ exist with respect to both metrics, it follows that $\Gamma(d)\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n \leq \Gamma(\hat{d})\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$ (See [5, Remark 1.9]).

Proposition 1.16

Let $f, f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If $f = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$, then f is lower semicontinuous.

Proof. Assume for contradiction that f is not lower semicontinuous, that is there exists $x \in X$ and a sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, but $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) \leq f(x) - \epsilon$ for some $\epsilon < 0$. Then since f_n Γ -converges to f , by property (ii) of Definition 1.13, we have that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) \geq f(x)$. Moreover, for each $x_n \in X$, there exists a sequence $(y_m^n)_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $y_m^n \xrightarrow{d} x_n$ as $m \rightarrow \infty$, and by property (ii) of Definition 1.13 and Remark 1.14, $\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} f_m(y_m^n) = f(x_n)$. We also clearly have that $y_n^n \xrightarrow{d} x$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, thus by Γ -convergence $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(y_n^n) \geq f(x)$. But for $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $M \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall m \geq M$ we have $|f_m(y_m^n) - f(x_n)| < \epsilon$. Then since $f_n(y_n^n) = f_n(y_n^n) - f(x_n) + f(x_n)$, we have that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(y_n^n) \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n(y_n^n) - f(x_n)) + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) < f(x) - \epsilon$,¹ which contradicts the previous statement. Hence, f must be lower semicontinuous. \square

Theorem 1.17 (Stability Under Continuous Perturbations)

Let $f, g, f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$ and g is continuous. Then $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + g) = f + g$.

Proof. The result follows directly by the application of the definition of Γ -convergence and also the sequential definition of continuity, i.e. for any sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq X$ such that $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x \in X$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} g(x_n) = g(x)$. \square

Proposition 1.18

Let $f, g, f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If $f = \Gamma\text{-}\lim f_n$ and f_n converges to g pointwise as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $f \leq g$.

Proof. As $f_n \rightarrow g$ pointwise, we have that $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = g(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Moreover, for each $x \in X$, the constant sequence $x_n = x$ converges to x as $n \rightarrow \infty$, therefore by property (i) of Definition 1.13, $f(x) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = g(x)$ as required. \square

Proposition 1.19

Let $f, f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If $f_n \rightarrow f$ uniformly, then $\Gamma\text{-}\lim f_n = \text{l.s.c.}(f)$.

Proof. We prove this in two steps. Firstly, let $g : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be lower semicontinuous and such that $g \leq f = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$. Then taking the supremum of all such possible g 's, we get by the definition of the lower semicontinuous envelope, $\text{l.s.c.}(f) \leq \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$. Now since $f_n \rightarrow f$ uniformly, we have that $f_n \rightarrow f$ pointwise. Then by Proposition 1.18 $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n \leq f$. But by Proposition 1.16, $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$ is lower semicontinuous by, and therefore $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n \leq \text{l.s.c.}(f)$. Hence $\text{l.s.c.}(f) = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$, as required. \square

Proposition 1.20 ([12, Remark 5.5])

Let $f, f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$. If $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence of lower semicontinuous functions and $f_n \nearrow f$ pointwise increasingly as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then f is lower semicontinuous, and $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$.

Corollary 1.21

Let $f, f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be such that $f_n = f$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = \text{l.s.c.}(f)$.

Proof. The sequence of constant functions f_n converges uniformly to the function f . Thus by Proposition 1.19, the result follows. \square

¹Since for any sequence a_n and b_n , $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} (a_n + b_n) \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} a_n + \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} b_n$.

Definition 1.22 (Γ -lower/upper Limit)

Let $f_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $x \in X$. Then the Γ -lower limit of the sequence $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ at x is defined as:

$$\Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = \inf\{\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \mid x_n \rightarrow x\}.$$

The Γ -upper limit of the sequence $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ at x is defined as:

$$\Gamma\text{-}\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = \inf\{\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \mid x_n \rightarrow x\}.$$

We say that the Γ -limit of the sequence $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ at x is $\alpha \in \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ if:

$$\Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = \alpha = \Gamma\text{-}\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x).$$

In this case we write $\alpha = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x)$.

Furthermore, we say that a sequence functions $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ Γ -converges to some function f if and only if for all $x \in X$ the Γ -limit exists and is equal to $f(x)$.

Remark 1.23

Definition 1.22 gives a new characterisation of what it means to be a Γ -limit, and provides an alternate view. In fact, there are many different equivalent definitions of Γ -convergence, all useful in their own way. We shall mainly stick to our first definition of Γ -convergence given in Definition 1.13, and only really use Definition 1.22 as a useful tool in proofs. To prove equivalence of the above definitions, one can prove this directly or see [5, Remark 1.6].

Proposition 1.24

Let $f, f_n, g, g_n : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be sequences of functions for $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$ and $f_n \rightarrow f$ pointwise, and if $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} g_n = g$ and $g_n \rightarrow g$, then as long as the functions $f_n + g_n$ and $f + g$ are well defined for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + g_n) = f + g$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + g_n) = f + g$ pointwise.

Proof. By the definition Γ -convergence through the upper and lower Γ -limits, Definition 1.22,

$$f + g = \Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n + \Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} g_n,$$

then by [11, Proposition 6.17], it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + g_n) \\ &\leq \Gamma\text{-}\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + g_n) \end{aligned}$$

and by the definition of the upper Γ -limit

$$\leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + g_n) = f + g,$$

where the last equality follows by pointwise converge of f_n to f and g_n to g , and hence $f_n + g_n$ to $f + g$. \square

Proposition 1.25 (Well Definedness of Γ -convergence)

Let $f_n, f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and assume that $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$. Then every subsequence $(f_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ also Γ -converges to f .

Proof. By the definition of Γ -convergence in the sense of upper and lower Γ -limits, it follows directly that for any subsequence $(f_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that

$$\Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n \leq \Gamma\text{-}\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} f_{n_k}, \quad \text{and} \quad \Gamma\text{-}\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n \leq \Gamma\text{-}\limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} f_{n_k}.$$

Now since $f = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n$, we have that $f = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} f_{n_k}$, as required. \square

Theorem 1.26 (Fundamental Theorem of Γ -convergence)

Let $f_n, f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and assume that:

- (i) $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$;
- (ii) $x_n \in X$ is a minimiser of f_n for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$;
- (iii) $x_n \xrightarrow{d} x \in X$.

Then x is a minimiser of f .

Proof. Let $y \in X$. Then since $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$, there exists a recovery sequence $(y_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n = y$ and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(y_n) \leq f(y)$. Then

$$f(y) \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(y_n) \geq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) \geq f(x),$$

where the last inequality follows since $x_n \rightarrow x$ and by Γ -convergence of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ to f . Since $y \in X$ was chosen arbitrarily, this holds for all $y \in X$, and hence x minimises f as required. \square

1.2.1 Examples

To get used to the concept of Γ -convergence, it is useful to cover a number of examples. Here are a few examples where we compute the Γ -limit explicitly.

Example 1.27

Let $f_n : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be defined as $f_n(x) = nx e^{-2n^2 x^2}$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}$, see Figure 1.1. We aim to find a function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that satisfies both of the conditions in Definition 1.13. As a note, it is useful to notice that $f_n \rightarrow 0$ pointwise, as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Now, to determine a function that satisfies the $\Gamma\text{-}\liminf$ property, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we determine the minimum of f_n . Computing the derivative of $f_n(x)$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we find that the minimum of $f_n(x)$ is attained at $x = -\frac{1}{2n}$ where $f_n(x) = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{e}}$. Therefore we can safely say that for $x \in \mathbb{R}$, we have $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \geq -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{e}}$ since the pointwise limit of f_n is the zero function. Now a good candidate for the Γ -limit of $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ would be the lower semicontinuous function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{e}} & \text{if } x = 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

This is because f clearly satisfies the $\Gamma\text{-}\liminf$ condition since $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) \geq f(x)$ for any sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that converges to $x \in \mathbb{R}$. If $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to 0, then since $f(0) = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{e}}$,

Figure 1.1: Plot of the functions f_n for $n = 1, 2, 3$ in Example 1.27. It can be seen that as n gets very large, the functions f_n become very tight about the y -axis.

Figure 1.2: Plot of the functions f and h in Example 1.30, f on the left and g on the right. Hollow points on the plot imply a strict inequality at that point and solid points imply that point is satisfied by f at that value of x .

our Γ -lim inf condition is satisfied, as $f(0) \leq f_n(y)$ for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $y \in \mathbb{R}$. If a sequence x_n converges to $x \neq 0$, then $f(x) = 0$ and $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) = \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} nx_n e^{-2(nx_n)^2} = 0$.

The function f also satisfies the Γ -lim sup condition. To prove this, we consider two cases, $x = 0$ and $x \neq 0 \in \mathbb{R}$: if $x = 0$, then we find that the sequence $x_n = -\frac{1}{2n}$ is a recovery sequence since it converges to 0, and from before satisfies the condition $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) = -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{e}} = f(0)$. If $x \neq 0$, then the constant sequence $x_n = x$ forms a recovery sequence, since $x_n \rightarrow x$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x_n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) = 0 = f(x)$ (noting that $f_n \rightarrow 0$ pointwise). We can therefore conclude that the Γ -limit of the sequence $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is the function f defined above.

Example 1.28

Let f_n and f be as in Example 1.27. Then by a similar method to before, one can deduce that $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (-f_n) = f$. Which therefore implies that:

$$\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n + (-f_n)) = 0 \neq 2f = \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (f_n) + \Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (-f_n).$$

Remark 1.29

Therefore, as a consequence of Example 1.28, we can conclude that the Γ -limit is not linear.

Example 1.30

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $f_n = f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ where

$$f(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x < 1/2, \\ 0 & \text{if } x \geq 1/2. \end{cases} \quad (1.3)$$

The sequence f_n is constant, and f is lower semicontinuous. Therefore, by Corollary 1.21, $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n = f$.

Now instead, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, consider $h_n = h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ where

$$h(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 1/2, \\ 0 & \text{if } x > 1/2. \end{cases} \quad (1.4)$$

Since $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} h_n(1/2 + 1/n) = 0 < 1 = h(1/2)$, h is not lower semicontinuous. The function h is therefore not a good candidate for being a Γ -limit of the sequence $(h_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. But by Proposition 1.21, we have instead that $\Gamma\text{-}\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} h_n = \text{l.s.c.}(h)$, where in fact $\text{l.s.c.}(h)$ is the function

f from (1.3).

See Figure 1.2 for plots of the functions f and g defined in (1.3) and (1.4) respectively.

1.3 Some Measure Theory

In this section, we cover results required in the following chapters, in particular results regarding weak convergence of measures. We begin by defining what it means to be a μ -negligible set for measures μ .

Definition 1.31 (μ -negligible sets)

Let (X, Σ, μ) be a measure space.

- (i) A set $Y \subseteq X$ is said to be μ -negligible if there exists $E \in \Sigma$ such that $Y \subseteq E$ and $\mu(E) = 0$.
- (ii) A property $P(x)$ for $x \in X$ is said to hold μ -a.e in X if the set where P fails is μ -negligible.

Definition 1.32 (Absolute Continuity)

Suppose that (X, Σ, μ) is a σ -finite measure space. Let $\mathcal{N} = \{A \in \Sigma \mid \mu(A) = 0\}$. Suppose that ν is another σ -finite measure on the measurable space (X, Σ) . We say that ν is absolutely continuous with respect to μ if $\nu(A) = 0$ for all $A \in \mathcal{N}$. We shall denote this by writing $\nu \ll \mu$. In particular, a measure on $(X, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^2))$ is called absolutely continuous if it is absolutely continuous with respect to the 2-dimensional Lebesgue measure, \mathcal{L}^2 , where $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ denotes the Borel σ -algebra on \mathbb{R}^2 .

Theorem 1.33 (Radon-Nikodym Theorem, See [10, Theorem 4.2.2])

Let (X, Σ) be a measurable space, and let μ, ν be σ -finite positive measures on (X, Σ) . If ν is absolutely continuous with respect to μ , then there exists a Σ -measurable function $f : X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that for all $A \in \Sigma$

$$\nu(A) = \int_A f \, d\mu,$$

where f is unique up to μ -negligible sets.

For general use purposes, we now give a definition of the convolution of functions with measures.

Definition 1.34 (Convolution with Measures)

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. If $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^2)$, then we call the function

$$\mu * f(x) := \int_{\Omega} f(x - y) d\mu(y),$$

the convolution between f and μ whenever this makes sense.

Remark 1.35

Note that in the sense of standard convolutions, there is no function $f \in L^1_{\text{loc}}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $f * u = u$ for every continuous function u , whereas in terms of convolving with measures, such a measure does exist, in particular the Dirac delta δ_0 .

1.3.1 Weak Convergence of Measures

Within this subsection, we shall outline some of the key results that arise in measures spaces under weak convergence. We begin with the discussion on the construction of the weak convergence on \mathcal{M} .

Consider the set $C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of continuous and bounded function on \mathbb{R}^2 . Then by the Riesz representation theorem, for every bounded linear functional, I , on $C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$, there exists a unique Borel measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that

$$I(f) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu,$$

holds for each $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$. In fact, the norm of I coincides with the total variation of μ , i.e. $|\mu|$. This means that the dual space of $C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ is the space $(C_b(\mathbb{R}^2))^* = \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of all signed Borel measures on \mathbb{R}^2 . Then the weak* topology on $\mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ is the topology that describes pointwise convergence of linear functionals. That is, a sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ converges to a measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ weakly* if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_n(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu(x),$$

for all $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Such a topology does exist; in fact $\mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ is metrizable, under the metric

$$d(\mu, \nu) := \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^i \|f_i\|} \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_i \, d\mu - \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_i \, d\nu \right|,$$

where $(f_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a countably dense sequence in $C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ and $\|\cdot\| = \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^2} |\cdot(x)|$ represents the supremum norm. Then, under this topology, it can easily be seen that if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(\mu_n, \mu) = 0$, it follows that μ_n converges to μ weakly*.

We now restrict to the case of probability measures on \mathbb{R}^2 , $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, and write down the above discussion rigorously, and drop the '*' when discussing weak* convergence. We first define the support of a measure.

Definition 1.36 (Support of a Measure)

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Then the *support* of μ is defined as

$$\text{supp}(\mu) = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \mu(B_r(x)) > 0 \, \forall r > 0\}.$$

Definition 1.37 (Weak Convergence of Measures)

A sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of probability measures is said to converge weakly in the sense of measures to $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu_n = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu,$$

for all $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$. We denote this by $\mu_n \rightarrow \mu$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Remark 1.38

In the sense of functional analysis, weak convergence of measures should really be called weak* convergence of measures, but typically, the star is omitted. Weak convergence is often also known as narrow convergence, convergence in the sense of distribution, and as vague convergence.

Definition 1.39 (Tightness)

A sequence of probability measures $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ is called *tight* if for all $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ and a compact set $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, such that $\forall n > n_0$, we have $\mu_n(K) > 1 - \epsilon$.

Theorem 1.40 (Prokhorov's Theorem)

Let $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be a tight sequence of probability measures. Then there exists a subsequence of probability measures $(\mu_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ that converges weakly in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$.

Lemma 1.41 (See [27, Lemma 1.6])

Let $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be a sequence of probability measures and $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Then for all lower semicontinuous functions $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ that are bounded from below, we have

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu_n \geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu.$$

Proof. Since f is lower semicontinuous, by Theorem 1.7 and Remark 1.8, there exists a sequence of bounded continuous functions $(f_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $f_n \nearrow f$ pointwise increasingly as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then it follows that, since $\mu_n \rightarrow \mu$ weakly in the sense of measures, for some $m \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu_n \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_m \, d\mu_n = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_m \, d\mu.$$

Then by taking the limit as $m \rightarrow \infty$, by the monotone convergence theorem,

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu_n \geq \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_m \, d\mu = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu,$$

which is the required result. \square

Corollary 1.42

Let $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be a sequence of probability measures and $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Then for all upper semicontinuous functions $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ that are bounded from above, we have

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu_n \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f \, d\mu.$$

Proof. The proof follows by applying Lemma 1.41 to $-f$. \square

Proposition 1.43

Let $\mu, \mu_n, \nu, \nu_n \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $\mu_n \rightarrow \mu$ and $\nu_n \rightarrow \nu$ weakly in the sense of measures as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then $\mu_n \otimes \nu_n \rightarrow \mu \otimes \nu$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ weakly in the sense of measures.

Proof. Let $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be chosen arbitrarily. Then, by Stone-Weierstrass, there exists a sequence of linear combination of functions $h_i(x, y) = f_i(x)g_i(y)$, where $f_i, g_i \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$, that converge uniformly to f . Then by Fubini's theorem and by the linearity of the integral, it follows directly that

$$\sum_i \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} f_i(x)g_i(y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\nu_n(y) = \sum_i \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_i(x) \, d\mu_n(x) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} g_i(y) \, d\nu_n(y) \right).$$

Taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ and using Fubini's theorem once again, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_i \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_i(x) \, d\mu_n(x) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} g_i(y) \, d\nu_n(y) \right) &= \sum_i \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f_i(x) \, d\mu(x) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} g_i(y) \, d\nu(y) \\ &= \sum_i \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} f_i(x)g_i(y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\nu(y), \end{aligned}$$

and the result follows by taking the uniform limit of the approximation of the function f . \square

1.3.2 Push-forward of Measures

In this subsection, we briefly touch results regarding the change variables with respect to measures, which are done by the means of a push-forward. We start with the definition of the push-forward.

Definition 1.44 (Push-forward)

Let (X, Σ, μ) be a measure space, let Y be a set and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Then

(i) the *push-forward σ -algebra* $f(\Sigma)$ on Y is the collection

$$f(\Sigma) := \{S \subseteq Y \mid f^{-1}(S) \in \Sigma\};$$

(ii) the *push-forward* of μ by f is the measure $\nu : f(\Sigma) \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ defined by

$$\nu(S) = \mu(f^{-1}(S)).$$

The push-forward of μ by f , ν , is usually denoted as $\nu := f\#\mu$.

Proposition 1.45

Let (X, Σ, μ) be a measure space and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Then:

$$\int_Y g \, d(f\#\mu) = \int_X g \circ f \, d\mu,$$

for every measurable function g on Y .

Proof. It suffices to prove this result for simple functions, since by well known techniques, the result must then also hold for all measurable functions g . Therefore, let $g = 1_E$ for a Borel set $E \subseteq Y$. Then since $1_{f^{-1}(E)}(x) = 1_E(f(x))$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_Y g(x) \, d(f\#\mu)(x) &= \int_E d(f\#\mu)(x) = (f\#\mu)(E) = \mu(f^{-1}(E)) \\ &= \int_X 1_{f^{-1}(E)}(x) \, d\mu(x) = \int_X 1_E(f(x)) \, d\mu(x) = \int_X g \circ f(x) \, d\mu(x). \end{aligned}$$

Then by linearity, the result also holds for all simple functions, that is functions of the form $g(x) = \sum_i^n a_i 1_{E_i}(x)$ for $a_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and Borel sets $E_i \subseteq Y$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$, where $n \in \mathbb{N}$. \square

1.4 Primer on the Fourier Transform

In this section, we outline some basic results in Fourier analysis that will become useful later on in this thesis. We begin by defining the Schwarz space.

Definition 1.46 (Schwarz Space)

The *Schwarz space* $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of rapidly decreasing functions is defined as

$$\mathcal{S} := \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^2) = \left\{ f \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^2, \mathbb{C}) \mid |f|_{\alpha, \beta} := \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}^2} |x^\alpha \partial^\beta f(x)| < \infty \text{ for any } \alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{N}_0^2 \right\},$$

where we recall that $\mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Then we call the dual space of \mathcal{S} , \mathcal{S}' , the space of tempered distributions of \mathcal{S} , i.e.

$$\mathcal{S}' := \mathcal{S}'(\mathbb{R}^2) = \{T \in C_L(\mathcal{S}, \mathbb{C}) \mid \exists k, C_k \in \mathbb{R}, \text{ such that } |T(\varphi)| \leq C_k \|\varphi\|_k \forall \varphi \in \mathcal{S}\},$$

where $C_L(\mathcal{S}, \mathbb{C})$ denotes the space of all continuous linear operators $\mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$.

We now give the definition of the Fourier transform on the Schwarz space.

Definition 1.47 (Fourier Transform)

For $f \in \mathcal{S}$, the Fourier transform of f , denoted by \hat{f} , is defined as

$$\hat{f}(\xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} e^{-ix \cdot \xi} f(x) \, dx.$$

For $g \in \mathcal{S}$, the inverse Fourier transform of g , denoted by \check{g} , is defined as

$$\check{g}(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} e^{ix \cdot \xi} g(\xi) \, d\xi.$$

Theorem 1.48

The Fourier transform gives an isomorphism $\hat{\cdot} : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$. with inverse $\check{\cdot}$.

Corollary 1.49

The Fourier transform extends by continuity to an isomorphism $\hat{\cdot} : \mathcal{S}' \rightarrow \mathcal{S}'$ with inverse $\check{\cdot}$.

In particular, by Corollary 1.49, we define the Fourier transform of tempered distributions $T \in \mathcal{S}'$ by

$$\langle \hat{T}, \varphi \rangle := \langle T, \hat{\varphi} \rangle,$$

for all Schwartz functions $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$.

Lemma 1.50

Let $f, g \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^2)$, then $\widehat{f * g} = \hat{f}\hat{g}$. In fact, the result also holds if $f, g \in \mathcal{S}$.

Proof. We have by the definition of the Fourier transform

$$\widehat{f * g}(\xi) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} e^{-ix \cdot \xi} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x - y)g(y) \, dy \, dx,$$

then by Fubini's theorem, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} e^{-i(x-y) \cdot \xi} f(x - y) \, dx \right) e^{-iy \cdot \xi} g(y) \, dy \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \hat{f}(\xi) e^{-iy \cdot \xi} g(y) \, dy \\ &= \hat{f}(\xi) \hat{g}(\xi), \end{aligned}$$

which is exactly what was claimed. □

Chapter 2

Classical Case of Logarithmic Interactions

In this chapter, we shall study in detail a nonlocal energy functional of the form

$$I(\mu) := \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\mu(x) \quad (2.1)$$

where $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$. This functional represents the mean field energy of the discrete interaction energy of a Coulomb gas,

$$I_n(x_1, \dots, x_n) = -\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i \neq j} \log|x_i - x_j| + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|^2,$$

where $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in (\mathbb{R}^2)^n$ denote the positions of n particles in the plane (i.e. in \mathbb{R}^2).

Remark 2.1

We may view I_n as being defined on the space $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of probability measures in \mathbb{R}^2 through the one-to-one correspondence

$$\nu : (\mathbb{R}^2)^n \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2), \quad \nu(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}, \quad (2.2)$$

which associates, to a configuration of n points in \mathbb{R}^2 , the probability measure μ_n , the *empirical measure*. Therefore, for any $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, we may define I_n as

$$I_n(\mu) = \begin{cases} I_n(x_1, \dots, x_n) & \text{if } \mu = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}, \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

2.1 The Mean-Field Energy

We are interested in the minimisers of (2.3), which represent the optimal configuration of a Coulomb gas. For this, we shall instead study minimisers of the *continuum* functional $I : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by

$$I(\mu) = - \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \log|x-y| \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu(x). \quad (2.4)$$

But first, to make sure that the minimisers of I_n are well approximated by the minimisers of I , we show that I is the Γ -limit of I_n as $n \rightarrow \infty$. This interaction energy I is commonly referred to as the *mean-field energy* of I_n .

We are first going to analyse some properties of the mean field energy I , and hence begin with Lemma 2.2.

Lemma 2.2

Let $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $(I(\mu_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is uniformly bounded in $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

- (i) μ_n is tight;
- (ii) up to extraction of a subsequence, μ_n converges weakly to some $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$;
- (iii) I is lower semicontinuous with respect to probability measures, i.e.

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I(\mu_n) \geq I(\mu).$$

Proof. (i) First note that for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$\begin{aligned} -\log|x-y| + \frac{1}{2}(|x|^2 + |y|^2) &= -\log|x-y| + \frac{1}{2e}(|x|^2 + |y|^2) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2e}\right)(|x|^2 + |y|^2) \\ &\geq -\log|x-y| + \frac{1}{2e}|x-y|^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2e}\right)(|x|^2 + |y|^2), \end{aligned}$$

and as $-\log|x-y| + \frac{1}{2e}|x-y|^2 \geq 0$, we have that

$$-\log|x-y| + \frac{1}{2}(|x|^2 + |y|^2) \geq \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2e}\right)(|x|^2 + |y|^2). \quad (2.5)$$

Then using (2.5), for every $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, we have

$$I(\mu) \geq \left(1 - \frac{1}{e}\right) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 d\mu(x). \quad (2.6)$$

This implies in particular that $\inf_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)} I(\mu) > -\infty$. Now let $(I(\mu_n))_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be uniformly bounded, namely such that there exists $C \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $I(\mu_n) \leq C$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. By (2.6), for all $R > 0$ and for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$\hat{C} \geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 d\mu_n(x) \geq \int_{\overline{B_R(0)}^c} |x|^2 d\mu_n(x) \geq R^2 \mu_n(\overline{B_R(0)}^c),$$

where $\hat{C} = \left(\frac{e}{e-1}\right)C$. Hence we have that $\mu_n(\overline{B_R(0)}^c) \leq \frac{\hat{C}}{R^2}$, which can be made arbitrarily small by making R large. Since $n \in \mathbb{N}$ was chosen arbitrarily, $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is tight.

(ii) Since $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is tight, by Prokhorov's Theorem, Theorem 1.40, $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a convergent subsequence $(\mu_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ which converges to some probability measure $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$.

(iii) Recall that for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we define $W(x) = -\log|x|$. By (ii), $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a subsequence $(\mu_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ that converges to some $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ weakly in the sense of measures. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we may write $I(\mu_{n_k})$ as

$$I(\mu_{n_k}) = \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2} d\mu_{n_k}(x) d\mu_{n_k}(y). \quad (2.7)$$

Then by (2.5), the integrand in (2.7) is continuous and bounded below. Therefore, since $\mu_{n_k} \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in the sense of measures in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, by Proposition 1.43, $\mu_{n_k} \otimes \mu_{n_k} \rightharpoonup \mu \otimes \mu$ weakly in the sense of measures in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2)$, and hence by Lemma 1.41,

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} I(\mu_{n_k}) \geq I(\mu).$$

□

2.1.1 Γ -convergence to the Mean Field Energy

Using Lemma 2.2, we now prove that the Γ -limit of the discrete Hamiltonian, I_n in (2.3), is the mean-field energy (2.4).

Theorem 2.3 (Γ -convergence of I_n)

The sequence of functions $(I_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, with $I_n : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ defined in (2.3), Γ -converges to the functional $I : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$, defined in (2.4), as $n \rightarrow \infty$, with respect to the weak convergence of measures. Namely,

(i) for any $\mu, \mu_n \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure, $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\mu_n) \geq I(\mu)$;

(ii) for all $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, there exists a sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\mu_n) \leq I(\mu)$.

Idea of Proof. To prove Γ -convergence of $(I_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ to I as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we show that they satisfy the definition of Γ -convergence, see Definition 1.13. In particular, we prove the Γ -lim sup inequality in multiple steps.

Step 0: We first reduce to working with measures μ which are absolutely continuous to the Lebesgue measure \mathcal{L}^2 , and those that have compact support.

Step 1: Choose an arbitrary measure $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ which has compact support and is absolutely continuous to \mathcal{L}^2 . Then we approximate the measure μ by μ^h by discretising the support of μ into squares of sidelength h , and defining μ^h to be the sum of the scaled characteristic measures on each square, which conserves the mass of μ restricted to each square.

Step 2: Now that we have obtained an approximation of the measure μ , we reduce the Γ -lim sup claim for the measure μ to the measure μ^h .

Step 3: Then we construct a recovery sequence for μ^h , and denote it by $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$.

Step 4: Finally we show that the Γ -lim sup inequality holds for the measure μ^h with recovery sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. \square

Proof. We recall that for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we define $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$.

(i) It suffices to show that if $\mu_n := \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i} \rightharpoonup \mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ weakly in measure as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(x_1, \dots, x_n) \geq I(\mu),$$

since if $\mu_n \neq \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}$, then $I_n(\mu_n) = +\infty$, and the result holds trivially. As $\mu_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}$,

$$I_n(\mu_n) = \iint_{\Delta^c} W(x-y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\mu_n(x), \quad (\star)$$

where we recall that Δ denotes the diagonal in $\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2$, $\Delta = \{(x, x) \mid x \in \mathbb{R}^2\}$. In the first term of the right hand side of (\star) , we truncate the integrand using $M > 0$ and obtain the following estimate:

$$\iint_{\Delta^c} W(x-y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) \geq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) - \frac{M}{n}. \quad (2.8)$$

To prove (2.8), first note that,

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) &\leq \iint_{\Delta^c} W(x-y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) \\ &\quad + \iint_{\Delta} M \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y). \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\iint_{\Delta} M \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) = M(\mu_n \otimes \mu_n)(\Delta) = M \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \delta_{x_i, x_j} = M \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n 1 = \frac{M}{n},$$

where for all $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$\delta_{a,b} = \begin{cases} 1 & a = b, \\ 0 & a \neq b, \end{cases}$$

the result for the estimate follows.

Now by (2.8),

$$I_n(\mu_n) \geq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2} \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) - \frac{M}{n}.$$

Hence,

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\mu_n) \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2} \, d(\mu_n \otimes \mu_n)(x, y).$$

Since the function $(x, y) \mapsto W(x-y) \wedge M + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2}$ is continuous and bounded below, by (2.5), by the weak convergence of $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ and by Proposition 1.43 the weak convergence of $\mu_n \otimes \mu_n$ to $\mu \otimes \mu$ in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2)$, we have by Proposition 1.41

$$\begin{aligned} \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2} \, d(\mu_n \otimes \mu_n)(x, y) \\ \geq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2} \, d(\mu \otimes \mu)(x, y) \\ = \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu(x). \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, since $(W(x-y) \wedge M) \nearrow W(x-y)$ pointwise increasingly as $M \rightarrow \infty$, by the monotone convergence theorem

$$\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \wedge M \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) = \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y).$$

In conclusion, it now follows that

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\mu_n) \geq I(\mu).$$

(ii) We need to construct a recovery sequence for each measure $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. First, we will demonstrate that we can reduce to working with measures which are absolutely continuous to the Lebesgue measure \mathcal{L}^2 with density $f \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^2)$ ¹.

Let $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be an arbitrary measure such that $I(\mu) < +\infty$ (note that (ii) is trivial if μ is such that $I(\mu) = +\infty$). Since $I(\mu)$ is bounded, by (2.6) in Lemma 2.2, given $\alpha > 0$ there exists a compact set K_α such that $\mu(K_\alpha) > 1 - \alpha$. We may then define

$$\mu_\alpha := \frac{\mu \llcorner K_\alpha}{\mu(K_\alpha)},$$

¹That is $\mu = f\mathcal{L}^2$ for some $f \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^2)$.

Figure 2.1: Process of discretisation of the measure μ . The grey square represents \tilde{Q}_k^h for some k , whilst a single hatched square represent Q_k^h . The sidelength of each square is h .

which is supported on the compact set K_α and is still a probability measure. Furthermore, we have that $I(\mu_\alpha) < I(\mu) - \frac{1-\mu(K_\alpha)^2}{\mu(K_\alpha)^2}$. Then $\mu_\alpha \rightharpoonup \mu$ in the weak sense of measures as $\alpha \rightarrow 0$, and $\limsup_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} I(\mu_\alpha) \leq I(\mu)$. Thus, it suffices to find a recovery sequence for measures with compact support. Namely, it suffices to find, for all $\alpha > 0$, a sequence $(\mu_n^\alpha)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $\mu_n^\alpha \rightharpoonup \mu_\alpha$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\mu_n^\alpha) \leq I(\mu_\alpha)$.

Now let μ be a probability measure with compact support. We can approximate μ with smooth mollifiers $\varphi_\eta \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^2)$ by setting $\mu_\eta = \varphi_\eta * \mu$. Then $\mu_\eta \rightharpoonup \mu$ in the weak sense of measures as $\eta \rightarrow 0$. Furthermore, it can be shown that $\limsup_{\eta \rightarrow 0} I(\mu_\eta) \leq I(\mu)$ (see [29]), thus by a diagonal argument, it suffices to prove the Γ -lim sup result for measures that have a smooth density and a compact support. We note that, since $V(x) = |x|^2$ is continuous, and since μ_η are compactly supported

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) d\mu_\eta = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) d\mu(x),$$

as $\eta \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, it suffices to construct a recovery sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure and:

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \iint_{\Delta^c} W(x-y) d\mu_n(x) d\mu_n(y) \leq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y). \quad (2.9)$$

The proof of (2.9) will be split into multiple steps, and we follow the proof of Theorem 3.3 in [22].

Step 1 - Approximation of the measure: Let $h > 0$ be fixed, and define the family of squares

$$\tilde{Q}^h := \{[0, 3h)^2 + 3h\mathbf{m} \mid \mathbf{m} \in \mathbb{Z}^2\}.$$

Let $(\tilde{Q}_k^h)_{k=1, \dots, N_h}$ be the squares in \tilde{Q}^h intersecting the support of μ , namely $\mu = \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \mu \llcorner \tilde{Q}_k^h$. Now for $k = 1, \dots, N_h$ let Q_k^h be defined as

$$Q_k^h := \{x \in \tilde{Q}_k^h \mid x + \boldsymbol{\lambda} \in \tilde{Q}_k^h \text{ for } \boldsymbol{\lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^2 \text{ with } \|\boldsymbol{\lambda}\|_\infty < |h|\}.$$

We can then approximate the measure μ by μ^h , which is defined as follows,

$$\mu^h := \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)}{h^2} \chi_{Q_k^h} \mathcal{L}^2, \quad (2.10)$$

where $\chi_{Q_k^h}$ is the characteristic function². Note that for brevity, when a measure is absolutely continuous to the Lebesgue measure, we shall often drop the \mathcal{L}^d at the end when writing the measures out for appropriate d 's. Then, $\mu^h \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ since

$$\mu^h(\mathbb{R}^2) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)}{h^2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \chi_{Q_k^h}(x) dx = \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) = \mu(\mathbb{R}^2) = 1,$$

since $\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \chi_{Q_k^h}(x) dx = h^2$. In addition, we can see that $\mu^h \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly as $h \rightarrow 0$.

Step 2 - Reducing the Claim to Approximating Measures: For μ^h defined as (2.10), the following inequality holds

$$\limsup_{h \rightarrow 0} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) d\mu^h(x) d\mu^h(y) \leq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y). \quad (2.11)$$

This means that we can prove the limsup result for patch-discretised measures only. To prove the (2.11), let $M > 0$. Then for $W_M := W \wedge M$, we have $W = W_M + (W - W_M)$. Then as W_M is continuous and bounded from above, we have by weak convergence of $\mu^h \rightharpoonup \mu$ as $h \rightarrow 0$, and by Lemma 1.42,

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{h \rightarrow 0} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W_M(x-y) d\mu^h(x) d\mu^h(y) &\leq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W_M(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y) \\ &\leq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y). \end{aligned}$$

To prove (2.11), it therefore suffices to show that

$$\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \limsup_{h \rightarrow 0} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} (W - W_M)(x-y) d\mu^h(x) d\mu^h(y) = 0. \quad (2.12)$$

As $W(x-y) = -\log|x-y|$, it is easy to see that if $W(x-y) > M$, then $|x-y| < R_M := e^{-M}$. Therefore, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} (W - W_M)(x-y) d\mu^h(x) d\mu^h(y) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \int_{B_{R_M}(y)} (W - W_M)(x-y) d\mu^h(x) d\mu^h(y) \\ &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y)} W(x-y) d\mu^h(x) \right) d\mu^h(y), \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality follows since for $|x-y| < R_M$, we have $W \geq W_M$. For every $k = 1, \dots, N_h$, and every $p = 1, \dots, P_k^h$ where $P_k^h = \left\lfloor \frac{R_M}{3h} \right\rfloor + 1$, let

$$I_{k,p}^h := \{1 \leq j \leq N_h \mid Q_j^h = Q_k^h + 3h(m, l), |m| \vee |l| = p\}^3.$$

² $\chi_{Q_j^h}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in Q_j^h, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y)} W(x-y) \, d\mu^h(x) \right) d\mu^h(y) \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{j=1}^{N_h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h)}{h^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y)} W(x-y) \chi_{Q_j^h}(x) \, dx \right) \chi_{Q_k^h}(y) \, dy \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{j=1}^{N_h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h)}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_j^h} W(x-y) \, dx \right) dy \\
&= \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{p=1}^{P_k^h} \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h)}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_j^h} W(x-y) \, dx \right) dy \\
&+ \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)^2}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_k^h} W(x-y) \, dx \right) dy.
\end{aligned}$$

One can prove geometrically that if $j \in I_{k,p}^h$, $x \in Q_j^h$ and $y \in Q_k^h$ we have that $|x-y| \geq (3p-1)h$, and as $W(x-y) = -\log|x-y|$, it follows that $W(x-y) \leq -\log|(3p-1)h|$. Therefore, dealing with each of the terms on the right hand side of the previous formulae separately, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h)}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_j^h} W(x-y) \, dx \right) dy \\
&\leq \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h)}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_j^h} -\log((3p-1)h) \, dx \right) dy \\
&\leq \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h) (-\log((3p-1)h)).
\end{aligned}$$

One can also prove geometrically that for $j \in I_{k,p}^h$, $x \in \tilde{Q}_j^h$ and $y \in \tilde{Q}_k^h$ we have that $|x-y| \leq 3\sqrt{2}(p+1)h$, thus $-\log(3\sqrt{2}(p+1)h) \leq W(x-y)$. Therefore

$$\iint_{\tilde{Q}_k^h \times \tilde{Q}_j^h} W(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) \geq -\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h) \log(3\sqrt{2}(p+1)h),$$

and hence

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h)}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_j^h} W(x-y) \, dx \right) dy \leq \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h) (-\log((3p-1)h)) \\
&= \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h) \left(-\log(3\sqrt{2}(p+1)h) + \log\left(\frac{3\sqrt{2}(p+1)}{3p-1}\right) \right) \\
&\leq \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \iint_{\tilde{Q}_k^h \times \tilde{Q}_j^h} W(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \left(\log\left(\frac{3\sqrt{2}(p+1)}{3p-1}\right) \right) \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h).
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we find that if $x, y \in Q_k^h$, then $|x-y| \leq h\sqrt{2}$, which implies that $-\log(h\sqrt{2}) \leq W(x-y)$. Now since $W(x-y) = -\log|x-y|$, we have that $W(x-y) \leq 1 - \log|x-y|$, which

³ $I_{k,p}^h$ represents the indices of the squares which are at a distance of $3p$ -squares away from the square Q_k^h . That is, the squares Q_j^h in some \tilde{Q}_j^h for $j \neq k$.

Figure 2.2: Discretisation of the approximating measure μ^h . The black points indicate the allocation of particles to the vertices of the imposed grid within some box Q_k^h .

implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)^2}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y) \cap Q_k^h} W(x-y) dx \right) dy &\leq \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)^2}{h^4} \int_{Q_k^h} \left(\int_{B_{h\sqrt{2}}(y) \cap Q_k^h} W(x-y) dx \right) dy \\ &\leq \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)^2 (1 - \log(h\sqrt{2})) \\ &\leq \iint_{\tilde{Q}_k^h \times \tilde{Q}_k^h} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y) + \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Combining the above inequalities together, we then get

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\int_{B_{R_M}(y)} W(x-y) d\mu^h(x) \right) d\mu^h(y) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{p=1}^{P_k^h} \left[\sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \iint_{\tilde{Q}_k^h \times \tilde{Q}_j^h} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y) + \left(\log \left(\frac{3\sqrt{2}(p+1)}{3p-1} \right) \right) \sum_{j \in I_{k,p}^h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \mu(\tilde{Q}_j^h) \right] \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \left[\iint_{\tilde{Q}_k^h \times \tilde{Q}_k^h} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y) + \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)^2 \right] \\ &\leq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times B_{R_M}(y)} W(x-y) d\mu(x) d\mu(y) + C \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \mu(B_{R_M}(y)) d\mu(y) \end{aligned}$$

for some constant $C \in \mathbb{R}$. We have that as $M \rightarrow \infty$, $R_M \rightarrow 0$. Then since $I(\mu) < \infty$ (as μ is compactly supported), the right hand side of the above equation tends to zero as $M \rightarrow \infty$, which proves (2.12), and thus (2.11) which is as required.

Step 3 - Construction of the Recovery Sequence for μ^h : Thanks to the previous steps, it now suffices to construct a recovery sequence for the measures μ^h to prove the lim sup inequality. Now let $h > 0$, and for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let μ_n^h denote the approximation of the measure μ^h defined as in (2.10),

$$\mu_n^h := \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} c_{k,n} \chi_{Q_k^h},$$

where the constants $c_{k,n}$ are chosen such that $\sqrt{n\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)} \in \mathbb{N}_0$ for every $k = 1, \dots, N_h$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu_n^h(Q_k^h) = \mu^h(Q_k^h)$.⁴ Now in view of the approximation of the measure μ^h , we construct the recovery sequence $\mu_n = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}$ by choosing the points $x_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that⁵

- to each square Q_k^h , we allocate $n\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)$ particles;
- in each square Q_k^h , choose $\sqrt{n\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}$ equispaced horizontal and vertical coordinates, to form a lattice. Then the particles will be located at the vertices of this imposed square grid within Q_k^h (as shown in Figure 2.2), and the distance between any two particles within the same square Q_k^h will satisfy

$$|x_i - x_j| \geq \frac{h}{\sqrt{n\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}} := L_k^n.⁶$$

Furthermore, by the way we constructed μ_n , it immediately follows that $\mu_n \llcorner Q_k^h \rightharpoonup \mu^h \llcorner Q_k^h$ weakly in the sense of measure as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for every $k = 1, \dots, N_h$. We thus have that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu^h$ weakly as $n \rightarrow \infty$. It therefore remains to prove that μ_n is in fact a recovery sequence.

Step 4 - Γ -lim sup Inequality for the Recovery Sequence: We now aim show that

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \iint_{\Delta^c} W(x - y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) \leq \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x - y) \, d\mu^h(x) \, d\mu^h(y). \quad (2.13)$$

For $k = 1, \dots, N_h$, and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we let J_k^n denote the set of indices of particles x_i (of n) contained in the square Q_k^h , i.e.

$$J_k^n := \{1 \leq i \leq n \mid x_i \in Q_k^h\}.$$

We may then expand the term within the limit of (2.13) as

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{\Delta^c} W(x - y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) &= \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\substack{i,j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n W(x_i - x_j) \\ &= \underbrace{\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\substack{k,l=1 \\ k \neq l}}^{N_h} \sum_{\substack{i \in J_k^n \\ j \in J_l^n}} W(x_i - x_j)}_{(\star)} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{\substack{i,j \in J_k^n \\ i \neq j}} W(x_i - x_j)}_{(\dagger)}. \end{aligned}$$

For (\star) , it then follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\substack{k,l=1 \\ k \neq l}}^{N_h} \sum_{\substack{i \in J_k^n \\ j \in J_l^n}} W(x_i - x_j) &= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{\substack{k,l=1 \\ k \neq l}}^{N_h} \iint_{Q_k^h \times Q_l^h} W(x - y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) \\ &\leq \sum_{\substack{k,l=1 \\ k \neq l}}^{N_h} \iint_{Q_k^h \times Q_l^h} W(x - y) \, d\mu^h(x) \, d\mu^h(y), \end{aligned}$$

⁴One can interpret μ_n^h as an intermediate approximation before constructing a recovery sequence. The measure μ_n^h is obtained by slightly redistributing the mass of the measure μ^h such that in each square Q_k^h , we assign the mass of $n\mu(Q_k^h)$ particles. To make sure that particles in each square are evenly distributed (in the square lattice) when making the discretisation in the next step, we choose $n\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)$ to be square.

⁵It is useful to note that, for brevity, we have omitted the n -dependence of x_i .

⁶ L_k^n denotes the size of the square grid in Q_k^h formed by the particle locations, i.e. distance between two adjacent lattice points in Q_k^h .

where the last inequality follows since $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu^h$ in the sense of measures as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and since W is continuous and bounded above on $Q_k^h \times Q_l^h$ for $k \neq l$ ⁷. For (\dagger) , let $M > 0$, and consider $W = W_M + (W - W_M)$, where $W_M = W \wedge M$. Since W_M is continuous and bounded from above, and $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu^h$ in the sense of measures as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{\substack{i,j \in J_k^n \\ i \neq j}} W_M(x_i - x_j) &= \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \iint_{Q_k^h \times Q_k^h} W_M(x - y) \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \iint_{Q_k^h \times Q_k^h} W_M(x - y) \, d\mu^h(x) \, d\mu^h(y), \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the fact that $\mu_n \otimes \mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu \otimes \mu$ weakly in the sense of measures as $n \rightarrow \infty$ since $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then combining (\star) and (\dagger) , the claim (2.13) follows if we show that

$$\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \sum_{\substack{i,j \in J_k^n \\ i \neq j}} (W - W_M)(x_i - x_j) = 0. \quad (2.14)$$

Then since $|x_i - x_j| < h$ for $x_i, x_j \in Q_k^h$, we can choose M large enough such that $R_M := e^{-M} < h$, after which $W(x - y) > M$. Then for each $k = 1, \dots, N_h$

$$\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \in J_k^n \\ i \neq j}} (W - W_M)(x_i - x_j) \leq \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \in J_k^n \\ |x_i - x_j| < R_M \\ i \neq j}} W(x_i - x_j). \quad (2.15)$$

Now let $P_k^n = \left\lfloor \frac{R_M}{L_k^n} \right\rfloor$, and for $p = 2, \dots, P_k^n$, define

$$J_k^n(i, p) := \{j \in J_k^n \mid (p-1)L_k^n \leq |x_i - x_j| < pL_k^n\},$$

i.e. the indices of particles that are contained within the *square annulus*, of inner radius $(p-1)L_k^n$ and outer radius pL_k^n , about the particle x_i in Q_k^h . Then, we can rewrite the right hand side of (2.15) as

$$\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{\substack{i,j \in J_k^n \\ |x_i - x_j| < R_M \\ i \neq j}} W(x_i - x_j) = \frac{1}{n^2} \underbrace{\sum_{i \in J_k^n} \sum_{p=2}^{P_k^n} \sum_{j \in J_k^n(i,p)} W(x_i - x_j)}_{\text{Summing over each annulus of every point}}.$$

Since J_k^n can be interpreted as a *square annulus*, we may estimate the cardinality of the set J_k^n using the area of an annulus

$$\#(J_k^n(i, p)) \leq C_1(p^2 - (p-1)^2) = C_1(2p+1),$$

for some constant $C_1 \in \mathbb{R}$. Furthermore, for $j \in J_k^n(i, p)$, since $(p-1)L_k^h \leq |x_i - x_j| < pL_k^h$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} W(x_i - x_j) &> -\log(pL_k^h), \\ \text{and } W(x_i - x_j) &\leq -\log((p-1)L_k^h). \end{aligned}$$

⁷Since $k \neq l$, for $x_i \in Q_k^h$ and $x_j \in Q_l^h$, we have that $|x_i - x_j| \geq 2h \implies W(x_i - x_j) = -\log|x_i - x_j| < -\log|2h|$.

Then using the bounds for W obtained above, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
(\ddagger) &:= \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i \in J_k^n} \sum_{p=2}^{P_k^n} \sum_{j \in J_k^n(i,p)} W(x_i - x_j) \leq \frac{\#J_k^n C_1}{n^2} \sum_{p=2}^{P_k^n} (2p+1) (-\log((p-1)L_k^n)) \\
&\leq \frac{\#J_k^n C_1}{n^2} \sum_{p=2}^{P_k^n} \left(\frac{2}{eL_k^n} + 3 \log \frac{1}{L_k^n} \right) \\
&\text{(for some constant } C \in \mathbb{R}) \leq \frac{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h) C}{n} \left(\frac{1}{L_k^n} + \log \frac{1}{L_k^n} \right) (P_k^n - 1) \\
&\text{(since } x \log x \leq x^2) \leq \frac{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h) C}{n} \left(\frac{R_M}{(L_k^n)^2} - \frac{1}{L_k^n} + \frac{R_M}{(L_k^n)^2} - \log \frac{1}{L_k^n} \right) \\
&\leq \frac{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h) C}{n} \left(\frac{2R_M n \mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}{h^2} - \frac{n^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}}{h} + \frac{h}{n^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}} \right) \\
&= \mu_n^h(Q_k^h) C \left(\frac{2R_M \mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}{h^2} - \frac{\sqrt{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}}{n^{\frac{1}{2}} h} + \frac{h}{n^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\mu_n^h(Q_k^h)}} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Then if we let $n \rightarrow \infty$, then the right hand side of (\ddagger) becomes $\frac{CR_M(\mu^h(Q_k^h))^2}{h^2}$, accounting for the fact that $\mu_n^h(Q_k^h) \rightarrow \mu^h(Q_k^h)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Then proceeding to let $M \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain that $\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (\ddagger) \leq 0$. Similarly, through a careful manipulation, one can obtain $\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (\ddagger) \geq 0$, which concludes that $\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (\ddagger) = 0$, proving (2.14). This in turn proves the claim (2.13) as required. Then since the Γ -lim sup result for the confinement potential V holds true, it follows that $\Gamma\text{-lim sup}_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n(\mu_n) \leq I(\mu)$, which concludes the proof. \square

Remark 2.4

Note that, to prove the claim of Theorem 2.3, in the proof, we only used the facts that $|x|^2$ is lower semicontinuous and bounded below, and that $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\log|x| + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \right) = +\infty$. Therefore, the claim of Theorem 2.3 also holds for a more general class of potentials, \mathcal{W} (the interaction potential) and \mathcal{V} (the confinement potential), that satisfy the following two conditions:

- (i) \mathcal{V} is lower semicontinuous and bounded below;
- (ii) $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \left(\mathcal{W}(x) + \frac{\mathcal{V}(x)}{2} \right) = +\infty$.

2.2 Minimisation of the Mean Field Energy

Now from Chapter 1, we deduced that Γ -convergence ensures that the minima of I_n are well approximated by the minima of I , and therefore, our next aim is to prove existence and uniqueness of minimisers of the mean field energy I . We note that since I is the Γ -lim of I_n by Theorem 2.3, I is lower semicontinuous by the properties of Γ limits.

To prove uniqueness of minimisers of I , we will prove strict convexity of I , which follows by Lemma 2.5, and has been extracted from [24, Lemma 1.8]. Furthermore, an alternative proof of strict convexity is provided in section 2.2.1.

Lemma 2.5

Let $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in \mathcal{M}^+(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be such $\mu_1(\mathbb{R}^2) = \mu_2(\mathbb{R}^2) < \infty$. Furthermore, for $i = 1, 2$ assume that μ_i

are compactly supported and that $\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} W * \mu_i \, d\mu_i < \infty$. If $\mu := \mu_1 - \mu_2 \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, then

$$E(\mu) := \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) \geq 0, \quad (2.16)$$

and is $E(\mu) = 0$ if, and only if $\mu \equiv 0$.

Sketch Proof. The main problem with establishing (2.16) is that $W := -\log$ is not always positive, and also that μ is a signed measure. Clearly, if $W \geq 0$ and $\mu \in \mathcal{M}^+(\mathbb{R}^2)$, then the statement above is clear. The main idea for the proof of this claim relies on the *unfolding* of the convolution present in (2.16), more precisely on writing (2.16) as a square and getting rid of the convolution. This fact can be proved by the realisation that we may write $-\log|x-y|$ as follows

$$-\log|x-y| = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_R(0)} \frac{1}{|z-x||z-y|} \, dz - c - \log R + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{R}\right), \quad (2.17)$$

where c is a constant [24, Proof of Lemma 1.8, page 33], $x, y \in \text{supp}\mu$, $x \neq y$ and R is large. Given the expansion of the logarithm as in (2.17), we then proceed by integrating $-\log|x-y|$ twice with respect to μ . Then by using Fubini, and the fact that $\mu(\mathbb{R}^2) = 0$,

$$E(\mu) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_R(0)} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{1}{|x-z|} \, d\mu(x) \right)^2 \, dz + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{R}\right).$$

Now letting $R \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain the non-negativity result of the integral

$$E(\mu) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{1}{|x-z|} \, d\mu(x) \right)^2 \, dz. \quad (2.18)$$

To determine that $E(\mu) = 0$ if, and only if $\mu \equiv 0$, we first notice that if $E(\mu) = 0$, then by (2.18),

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{1}{|x-z|} \, d\mu(z) = 0 \quad \text{a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^2. \quad (2.19)$$

But since the integral (2.19) is continuous for large x , (2.19) must vanish outside of a compact set. We then write $\frac{1}{|x-z|}$ as a complex power-series:

$$\frac{1}{|z-x|} = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{m+n} \binom{-1/2}{m} \binom{-1/2}{n} z^m \bar{z}^n e^{-i(m-n)\varphi} R^{-(m+n)},$$

where $x = Re^{i\varphi}$ and R is large. It follows that for large R and for $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{ik\varphi} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{1}{|z-Re^{i\varphi}|} \, d\mu(z) \, d\varphi \\ &= (-1)^k \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \binom{-1/2}{m} \binom{-1/2}{n} R^{-2m-k-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} z^m \bar{z}^{m+k} \, d\mu(z). \end{aligned}$$

Then as the power series vanishes for large values of R , we can deduce that we must have

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} z^m \bar{z}^j \, d\mu(z) = 0,$$

for all $m, j \in \mathbb{N}_0$. Then since by Stone-Weierstrass $(z^m \bar{z}^k)_{m,j \in \mathbb{N}_0}$ spans a dense linear subset of the space of continuous functions on the support of μ , it follows by the linearity of the integral that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu(x) = 0,$$

for all continuous functions f . Then $\mu \equiv 0$, which was as required. Conversely, if $\mu \equiv 0$, then $E(\mu) = 0$ follows trivially. \square

Theorem 2.6 (Existence and Uniqueness of the Equilibrium Measure)

Let I be as in (2.4). Then there exists $\mu_0 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $I(\mu_0) \leq I(\mu)$ for all $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Furthermore, the minimiser μ_0 is unique and has compact support.

Proof. Step 1 - Existence: Let $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$; then by (2.6)

$$I(\mu) \geq \left(1 - \frac{1}{e}\right) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 d\mu(x),$$

which shows that $\inf I \geq 0$. Moreover, $\inf I < +\infty$, which follows by considering the measure $\mu(x_1, x_2) := \mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner [0, 1](x_1) \otimes \delta_0(x_2)$ for $(x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} & \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| d(\mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner [0, 1](x_1) \otimes \delta_0(x_2)) d(\mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner [0, 1](y_1) \otimes \delta_0(y_2)) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \iint_{[0, 1] \times [0, 1]} -\log(x_1 - y_1)^2 dx_1 dy_1, \end{aligned}$$

and by letting $t = x_1, s = y_1$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &= -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left(\frac{d}{dt}(t-s)\right) \log(t-s)^2 dt ds \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \left[(t-s) \log(t-s)^2 \Big|_{t=0}^{t=1} - \int_0^1 2 dt \right] ds \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 (1-s) \log(1-s)^2 + s \log(s)^2 - 2 ds \\ &= 1 - 2 \int_0^1 s \log s ds \stackrel{8}{=} \frac{3}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

We also have that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} (x_1^2 + x_2^2) d(\mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner [0, 1](x_1) \otimes \delta_0(x_2)) = \int_0^1 x_1^2 dx_1 = \frac{1}{3}.$$

Hence $I(\mu) = \frac{11}{6}$, which proves that $\inf I < \infty$.

Now let $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be a minimising sequence for the functional I (i.e. such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I(\mu_n) = I(\mu)$). Then by Lemma 2.2, $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a tight sequence, and the sequence $(\mu)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ has a weakly convergent subsequence $(\mu_{n_k})_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ to some $\mu_0 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Now since I is lower semicontinuous, we have that for any $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$

$$I(\mu) \geq \inf_{\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)} I(\nu) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I(\mu_n) = \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} I(\mu_{n_k}) \geq I(\mu_0).$$

Hence there exists a minimiser of I in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, that being μ_0 , as required.

Step 2 - Compactness of the Support of a Minimiser: Let μ_0 be a minimiser of I , then $I(\mu_0) < \infty$. By the bound obtained in (2.5), there exists a compact set $K \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $\mu_0(K) > 0$ and for all $x, y \in K^c$

$$-\log|x-y| + \frac{1}{2}(|x|^2 + |y|^2) \geq I(\mu_0) + 1. \quad (2.20)$$

⁸Since $\int_0^1 x \log x dx = \frac{1}{2}x^2 \log x \Big|_0^1 - \frac{x^2}{4} \Big|_0^1 = -\frac{1}{4}$

Now suppose for contradiction that $\text{supp}\mu_0 \not\subseteq K$, then $\mu_0(K) < 1$. Define $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ as

$$\nu := \frac{\mu_0 \llcorner K}{\mu_0(K)},$$

then $\nu(K) = 1$, and by (2.20) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} I(\mu_0) &= \left(\iint_{K \times K} + \iint_{(K \times K)^c} \right) \left(-\log|x-y| + \frac{|x|^2 + |y|^2}{2} \right) d\mu(x) d\mu(y) \\ &> \mu_0(K)^2 I(\nu) + (1 - \mu_0(K)^2)(I(\mu_0) + 1). \end{aligned}$$

This implies that

$$I(\nu) < I(\mu_0) - \frac{1 - \mu_0(K)^2}{\mu_0(K)^2} < I(\mu_0),$$

which contradicts the minimality of μ_0 , hence $\text{supp}\mu_0 \subseteq K$, and thus μ_0 is compactly supported.

Step 3 - Uniqueness: To prove uniqueness, let $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be distinct measures that have compact support and finite interaction energy, and be such that they minimise the interaction energy I . Note that to ensure the uniqueness of the minimiser, it suffices to show that the functional I is strictly convex on probability measures with compact support and finite interaction energy.

Let $t \in (0, 1)$; then the probability measure $(1-t)\mu + t\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ has finite interaction energy and compact support. Moreover:

$$I((1-t)\mu + t\nu) = (1-t)I(\mu) + tI(\nu) - t(1-t)J(\mu - \nu, \mu - \nu),$$

where

$$J(\mu_1, \mu_2) := \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| d\mu_1(x) d\mu_2(x),$$

for $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ [20, Theorem 9.3]. Since $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ have compact support and finite logarithmic energy, and are such that $\mu(\mathbb{R}^2) - \nu(\mathbb{R}^2) = 0$, by Lemma 2.5, we have that $J(\mu - \nu) > 0$ ⁹. Thus we have that

$$I((1-t)\mu + t\nu) < (1-t)I(\mu) + tI(\nu) \quad \forall t \in (0, 1),$$

which proves strict convexity, and hence uniqueness. \square

2.2.1 Alternative Proof of Strict Convexity of Interaction Energy

In the proof of uniqueness in Theorem 2.6, the proof of strict convexity of the interaction energy heavily relied on Lemma 2.5, which utilised the fact that we may write the logarithmic potential in a convenient way. We are somewhat fortunate that this can be done, and this method doesn't give us much information on how to determine strict convexity of more general interaction energies. There is although a more general method to obtain strict convexity through the use of Fourier transforms. To prove strict convexity of I , and hence uniqueness on the set of probability measures with compact support and finite interaction energy, by Step 3 of the proof of Theorem 2.6, it is required that we show that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| d\omega(x) d\omega(y) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} -(\log * \omega)(y) d\omega(y) > 0, \quad (2.21)$$

⁹Not \geq since $\mu \neq \nu$.

where $\omega = \mu - \nu$, for all $\mu, \nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ with $\mu \neq \nu$, $(\mu - \nu)(\mathbb{R}^2) = 0$, and μ, ν with compact support and finite interaction energy. The idea in proving this using Fourier analysis comes from the fact that, at least formally, it is possible to rewrite (2.21) in Fourier space as:

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} W * \omega \, d\omega = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \hat{W}(\xi) |\hat{\omega}(\xi)|^2 \, d\xi, \quad (2.22)$$

where $W = -\log$. Now if we show that $\hat{W} > 0$, the result in (2.21) follows (modulo proving (2.21) rigorously). Since $\omega(\mathbb{R}^2) = 0$, it follows that $\hat{\omega}(0) = 0$ by the definition of the Fourier transform. Hence, it suffices to prove to $\hat{W} > 0$ for positive $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\varphi(0) = 0$.

We now compute the Fourier transform of the logarithm.

Proposition 2.7

The Fourier transform of $W(x) = -\log|x|$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is given by:

$$\langle \hat{W}, \varphi \rangle = \varphi(0) (\gamma + \log \pi) + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{|\xi|^2} (\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)) \, d\xi + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{1}{|\xi|^2} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi,$$

for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$, where γ denotes the Euler-Mascheroni constant.

Proof. We have that $W \in L_{loc}^1(\mathbb{R}^2)$ ¹⁰, and since W has logarithmic growth at infinity, W is a tempered distribution, i.e. is in \mathcal{S}' . Then since the Fourier transform is an automorphism on \mathcal{S}' , we have that $\hat{W} \in \mathcal{S}'$, where \hat{W} is defined as

$$\langle \hat{W}, \varphi \rangle := \langle W, \hat{\varphi} \rangle \quad \forall \varphi \in \mathcal{S}.$$

Let $P(x) = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \log|x|$ and for $\alpha \in (0, 2)$, let P_α denote the Riesz potential of order α , i.e.

$$P_\alpha(x) = \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) 2^\alpha \pi} (|x|^{\alpha-2} - 1),$$

where Γ denotes the Gamma function. Then since $\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}) = 2^{\frac{\Gamma(2-\frac{\alpha}{2})}{2-\alpha}}$, by l'Hôpital's rule, it follows that for arbitrary $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 2} P_\alpha(x) &= \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 2} \frac{\Gamma(2 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) 2^{\alpha-1} \pi (2 - \alpha)} (|x|^{\alpha-2} - 1) \\ &= \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 2} \frac{-\frac{1}{2} \Gamma'(2 - \frac{\alpha}{2}) (|x|^{\alpha-2} - 1) + \Gamma(2 - \frac{\alpha}{2}) |x|^{\alpha-2} \log|x|}{\frac{1}{2} \Gamma'(\frac{\alpha}{2}) 2^{\alpha-1} \pi (2 - \alpha) + \Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) \log(2) 2^{\alpha-1} \pi (2 - \alpha) - \Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) 2^{\alpha-1} \pi} \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \log|x| = P(x), \end{aligned}$$

that is,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 2} P_\alpha(x) = P(x) \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^2. \quad (2.23)$$

Hence, by (2.23) it follows that $\hat{P}_\alpha \rightarrow \hat{P}$ as $\alpha \rightarrow 2$ in the sense of tempered distributions, i.e. $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 2} \langle \hat{P}_\alpha, \varphi \rangle = \langle \hat{P}, \varphi \rangle$ for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$. Now it is known that [15, Chapter 4, Page 151]

$$\hat{P}_\alpha(\xi) = \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} - \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) 2^\alpha \pi} \delta_0(\xi), \quad \xi \in \mathbb{R}^2.$$

¹⁰Since for any compact set $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \int_{K \setminus B_\delta(0)} \log|x| \, dx < \infty$ (can prove by using l'Hôpital's rule).

Then taking the duality pairing of \hat{P}_α with some Schwartz function $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{P}_\alpha, \varphi \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} - \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2})2^\alpha\pi} \delta_0(\xi) \right) \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi - \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2})2^\alpha\pi} \varphi(0) \\
&= \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi + \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi - \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2})2^\alpha\pi} \varphi(0) \\
&= \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} (\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)) \, d\xi + \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(0) \, d\xi + \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi \\
&\quad - \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2})2^\alpha\pi} \varphi(0).
\end{aligned}$$

But, assuming $\alpha \leq 2$,

$$\int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(0) \, d\xi = \frac{\varphi(0)}{(2\pi)^{\alpha-1}(2-\alpha)}, \quad (2.24)$$

and hence it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{P}_\alpha, \varphi \rangle &= \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} (\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)) \, d\xi + \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\alpha-1}(2-\alpha)} - \frac{\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2})2^\alpha\pi} \right) \varphi(0).
\end{aligned}$$

Again, since $\Gamma(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2}) = 2^{\frac{\Gamma(2-\alpha)}{2-\alpha}}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \hat{P}_\alpha, \varphi \rangle &= \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} (\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)) \, d\xi + \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^\alpha} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) - \pi^{\alpha-2}\Gamma(2 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{(2-\alpha)} \right) \frac{\varphi(0)}{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2})(2\pi)^{\alpha-1}}.
\end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

It now suffices to take the limit of (2.25) as $\alpha \rightarrow 2^-$ (since (2.24) is only defined for $\alpha \leq 2$). First, by l'Hôpital's rule

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 2^-} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\frac{\alpha}{2}) - \pi^{\alpha-2}\Gamma(2 - \frac{\alpha}{2})}{(2-\alpha)} \right) = \gamma + \log \pi,$$

using the fact that $\Gamma(1) = 1$ and $\Gamma'(1) = -\gamma$. Now by passing to the limit as $\alpha \rightarrow 2^-$ of (2.25), we find that

$$\langle \hat{P}, \varphi \rangle = \frac{\varphi(0)}{2\pi} (\gamma + \log \pi) + \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^2} (\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)) \, d\xi + \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{1}{(2\pi|\xi|)^2} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi.$$

Then by multiplying across by 2π , we obtain the required result. We also take note that the integral over $|\xi| \leq 1$ is finite, even if $\frac{1}{|\xi|^2}$ is not in $L^1(\mathbb{R}^2)$, because $|\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)| = \mathcal{O}(|\xi|)$ as $\xi \rightarrow 0$, and so the right hand side of the above makes sense. \square

Remark 2.8

Proposition 2.7 implies that for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$ with $\varphi(0) = 0$, $\varphi \geq 0$ and $\varphi \not\equiv 0$:

$$\langle \hat{W}, \varphi \rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{\varphi(\xi)}{|\xi|^2} \, d\xi > 0.$$

From this it is not difficult to show that (2.22) holds true for $\omega \in \mathcal{S}$, and hence by an approximation argument (see proof of [23, Theorem 1.1]), the result of Proposition 2.7 also holds for measures in $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, and hence I is strictly convex, as required.

2.2.2 The Euler-Lagrange Conditions

In this subsection, we shall deduce the Euler-Lagrange conditions for the minimiser of the interaction energy functional $I : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ shown in (2.4).

We can in fact deduce an important property of the minimiser (equilibrium measure) before even deducing the Euler-Lagrange conditions, and that is that the unique minimiser of I , μ_0 , is radial. This follows from Lemma 2.10 which is stated for a more general class of potentials. We begin by defining what is a radial measure.

Definition 2.9 (Radial Measure)

A measure $\mu \in \mathcal{M}^+(\mathbb{R}^2)$ is said to be radial if for all rotations $R \in SO(2)$, we have that $R\#\mu = \mu$.

Lemma 2.10

Let $\mathcal{I} : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be defined as

$$\mathcal{I}(\mu) := \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(x - y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{V}(x) \, d\mu(x),$$

with $\mathcal{W} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{V} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ radial functions. If \mathcal{I} has a unique minimiser $\mu^* \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, then μ^* is a radial measure.

Proof. Let $R \in SO(2)$. Then since $\mathcal{W} \circ R = \mathcal{W}$ and $\mathcal{V} \circ R = \mathcal{V}$, we have that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}(R\#\mu^*) &= \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(x - y) \, d(R\#\mu^*(x)) \, d(R\#\mu^*(y)) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{V}(x) \, d(R\#\mu^*(x)) \\ &= \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(R(x) - R(y)) \, d\mu^*(x) \, d\mu^*(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{V}(R(x)) \, d\mu^*(x) \\ &= \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(R(x - y)) \, d\mu^*(x) \, d\mu^*(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{V}(R(x)) \, d\mu^*(x) \\ &= \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(x - y) \, d\mu^*(x) \, d\mu^*(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{V}(x) \, d\mu^*(x) = \mathcal{I}(\mu^*), \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows by Proposition 1.45. Thus $R\#\mu^*$ minimises \mathcal{I} also. But since we have assumed that the minimiser is unique, we must have that $R\#\mu^* = \mu^*$. Then μ^* is radial, since $R \in SO(2)$ was chosen arbitrarily, which is as required. \square

Now to determine the Euler-Lagrange conditions, we begin first by introducing a quantity called *capacity*.

Definition 2.11 (Capacity)

Let $\mathcal{W} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and let $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ be a compact set. Then the *capacity*, $\text{cap}_{\mathcal{W}}$, of K with respect to the potential \mathcal{W} is defined as

$$\text{cap}_{\mathcal{W}}(K) := \Psi \left(\inf_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}(K)} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(x - y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) \right), \quad \Psi(x) := e^{-x}.$$

Then for any set $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, we define the *capacity* as

$$\text{cap}_{\mathcal{W}}(A) = \sup_{\text{compact } K \subseteq A} \text{cap}_{\mathcal{W}}(K).$$

If $\mathcal{W} = W := -\log|\cdot|$, then $\text{cap}_{\mathcal{W}}$ is called the *logarithmic capacity*.

For the following, let $\mathcal{W} : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a general function.

Remark 2.12

We note that in Definition 2.11, the infimum can be $+\infty$, if for every $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(K)$

$$\iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \mathcal{W}(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) = +\infty.$$

Moreover, the capacity is a monotonically increasing set function.

Remark 2.13

Note that if $K = \{x_0\}$ for some $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^2$, then $\mathcal{P}(K) = \{\delta_{x_0}\}$. So for $W(x) = -\log|x|$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$,

$$\iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \, d\delta_{x_0}(x) \, d\delta_{x_0}(y) = +\infty,$$

and hence $\text{cap}_W(K) = 0$. Thus the logarithmic capacity does not *see* points. This in fact holds for a general class of functions \mathcal{W} that has a singularity at 0, i.e. $\mathcal{W}(0) = +\infty$.

We now define a concept very similar to that of *almost everywhere*.

Definition 2.14 (Quasi-everywhere)

We say that a property holds *quasi-everywhere* (q.e.) if it holds everywhere except on a set of capacity zero.

Lemma 2.15

Let $E \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, and $\mu \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be such that $\iint_{E \times E} \mathcal{W}(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) < \infty$. If $\text{cap}_W(E) = 0$ then $\mu(E) = 0$.

Proof. If $\text{cap}_W(E) = 0$, then

$$\inf_{\nu \in \mathcal{P}(E)} \iint_{E \times E} \mathcal{W}(x-y) \, d\nu(x) \, d\nu(y) = +\infty.$$

Assume for contradiction that $\mu(E) \neq 0$. Then define by η , the probability measure on \mathbb{R}^2

$$\eta := \frac{\mu \llcorner E}{\mu(E)},$$

(if μ is a negative measure, then just negate the above). Since $\iint_{E \times E} \mathcal{W}(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) < \infty$, it follows that $\iint_{E \times E} \mathcal{W}(x-y) \, d\eta(x) \, d\eta(y) < \infty$, which directly contradicts the fact that $\text{cap}_W(E) = 0$. Hence $\mu(E) = 0$. \square

Lemma 2.15 in particular states, for the case when $\mathcal{W} = W := -\log|\cdot|$, measures with compact support and finite interaction energy do not charge sets of zero capacity. A specific case of interest of Lemma 2.15 is the case when μ is the Lebesgue measure.

Corollary 2.16

Let $E \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ be a Borel measurable set. If $\text{cap}_W(E) = 0$, then $\mathcal{L}^2(E) = 0$.

Remark 2.17

In Corollary 2.16, it is useful to note that for $A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$, if $\mathcal{L}^2(A) = 0$ it does not necessarily follow that $\text{cap}_W(A) = 0$. Therefore, the capacity *sees* more sets than the Lebesgue measure.

Remark 2.18

If a property holds q.e., then the set on which it does not hold has capacity zero, and thus by Lemma 2.16, this set also has zero Lebesgue measure, and hence this property holds \mathcal{L}^2 -a.e.

In what follows, note that we only deal with the logarithmic capacity cap_W , since $W = -\log|\cdot|$

Theorem 2.19 (Euler-Lagrange Conditions)

The minimiser $\mu_0 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of I in (2.4) is uniquely characterised by the Euler-Lagrange conditions: there exists $c \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(i) \quad (W * \mu_0)(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq c, \quad \text{for q.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^2; \quad (\text{EL1})$$

$$(ii) \quad (W * \mu_0)(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} = c, \quad \text{for } \mu_0\text{-a.e. } x \in \text{supp}(\mu_0). \quad (\text{EL2})$$

In particular,

$$c := I(\mu_0) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\mu_0(x).$$

Proof. Recall that $W(x) := -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Let $\mu_0 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be the unique minimiser of I . Then consider small variations of this minimiser of the form $(1 - \epsilon)\mu_0 + \epsilon\nu$ where $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$ and $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ has compact support and is such that $I(\nu) < \infty$. Then since, μ_0 is a minimiser of I , it follows that

$$I(\mu_0) \leq I((1 - \epsilon)\mu_0 + \epsilon\nu) \quad \forall \epsilon \in (0, 1). \quad (2.26)$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} I((1 - \epsilon)\mu_0 + \epsilon\nu) &= \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x - y) \, d(\mu_0 + \epsilon(\nu - \mu_0))(x) \, d(\mu_0 + \epsilon(\nu - \mu_0))(y) \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\mu_0(x) + \epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d(\nu - \mu_0)(x) \\ &= I(\mu_0) + \epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} (2W * \mu_0(x) + V(x)) \, d(\nu - \mu_0)(x) \\ &\quad + \epsilon^2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} W * (\nu - \mu_0)(x) \, d(\nu - \mu_0)(x). \end{aligned}$$

By (2.26), and the expansion of $I((1 - \epsilon)\mu_0 + \epsilon\nu)$ obtained above, we obtain

$$\epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} (2W * \mu_0(x) + V(x)) \, d(\nu - \mu_0)(x) + \epsilon^2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} W * (\nu - \mu_0)(x) \, d(\nu - \mu_0)(x) \geq 0.$$

Since both $I(\mu_0), I(\nu) < \infty$, both of the integrals above are finite, and hence we can divide across by ϵ and let $\epsilon \rightarrow 0^+$, yielding the following identity

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} \right) \, d\nu(x) \geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} \right) \, d\mu_0(x) =: c. \quad (2.27)$$

Since $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ was chosen arbitrarily, the inequality (2.27) holds for all $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ which have compact support and have finite interaction energy. Moreover, it is easy to see that

$$c = I(\mu_0) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\mu_0(x),$$

where c is the constant defined in (2.27).

(i) We now prove (EL1), by following the approach in [29]. Assume for contradiction that (EL1) does not hold q.e. on \mathbb{R}^2 , i.e., by the definition of capacity, there exists a set $K \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ such that (EL1) does not hold on K and $\text{cap}_W(K) > 0$. Since the capacity of a generic set is defined as the supremum of the capacities of compact sets included in K , we may assume

without loss of generality that K is compact. Furthermore, by the definition of capacity, there exists a probability measure $\eta \in \mathcal{P}(K)$ such that

$$\iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \, d\eta(x) \, d\eta(y) < \infty$$

(since otherwise, the capacity of K would be equal to zero). Furthermore $-W * \mu_0$ is bounded above on any compact set of \mathbb{R}^2 since $-W = \log$ is bounded above on any compact set and μ_0 has compact support. Then, since (EL1) does not hold on K , in (EL1), we may rearrange for V to obtain that $V < 2c - 2W * \mu_0$ pointwise on K , which is bounded above since K is compact and by the previous comment. Now since η is supported on K , by integrating both sides with respect to η yields

$$\int_K V(x) \, d\eta(x) < \int_K (2c - 2W * \mu_0(x)) \, d\eta(x) < \infty, \quad (2.28)$$

since the integrand is finite, and the integral is over a compact set. Therefore

$$I(\eta) = \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W(x-y) \, d\eta(x) \, d\eta(y) + \int_K V(x) \, d\eta(x) < \infty.$$

But since η is compactly supported, by (2.27)

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} \right) \, d\eta(x) \geq c.$$

But this directly contradicts (2.28), hence (EL1) must hold true q.e. in \mathbb{R}^2 .

(ii) Let $L := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} < c\}$. By (i), $\text{cap}_W(L) = 0$, and since μ_0 has compact support and is such that $I(\mu_0) < \infty$, then by Lemma 2.15, $\mu_0(L) = 0$. Therefore,

$$W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} \geq c \quad \text{for } \mu_0\text{-a.e. } x \in \text{supp}(\mu_0).$$

Then integrating over \mathbb{R}^2 with respect to μ_0 ,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} \right) \, d\mu_0(x) \geq c.$$

Moreover, by (2.27), we must have that

$$W * \mu_0(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} = c, \quad \text{for } \mu_0\text{-a.e. } x \in \text{supp}(\mu_0),$$

which is exactly (EL2). To prove that (EL1) and (EL2) uniquely characterise the equilibrium measure μ_0 , assume that there exists $\tilde{c} \in \mathbb{R}$ and another measure $\nu_0 \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} (i) \quad & (W * \nu_0)(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq \tilde{c}, \quad \text{for q.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^2; \\ (ii) \quad & (W * \nu_0)(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} = \tilde{c}, \quad \text{for } \nu_0\text{-a.e. } x \in \text{supp}(\nu_0), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\tilde{c} = I(\nu_0) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} V(x) \, d\nu_0(x),$$

which are the corresponding Euler-Lagrange conditions for the probability measure ν_0 .

For $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$, let $\mu_\epsilon := (1 - \epsilon)\mu_0 + \epsilon\nu_0$. Then using the distributivity of convolutions and the Euler-Lagrange conditions for both μ_0 and ν_0 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} I(\mu_\epsilon) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} (W * ((1 - \epsilon)\mu_0 + \epsilon\nu_0) + V) \, d\mu_\epsilon \\ &= (1 - \epsilon) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0 + \frac{V}{2} \right) \, d\mu_\epsilon + \epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \nu_0 + \frac{V}{2} \right) \, d\mu_\epsilon + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\mu_\epsilon \\ &= (1 - \epsilon) \left[(1 - \epsilon) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0 + \frac{V}{2} \right) \, d\mu_0 + \epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \mu_0 + \frac{V}{2} \right) \, d\nu_0 \right] \\ &\quad + \epsilon \left[(1 - \epsilon) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \nu_0 + \frac{V}{2} \right) \, d\mu_0 + \epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \left(W * \nu_0 + \frac{V}{2} \right) \, d\nu_0 \right] + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\mu_\epsilon, \end{aligned}$$

now applying the Euler-Lagrange conditions and noting that $\mu_0(\mathbb{R}^2) = 1 = \nu_0(\mathbb{R}^2)$ yields

$$\geq (1 - \epsilon)[(1 - \epsilon)c + \epsilon c] + \epsilon[(1 - \epsilon)\tilde{c} + \epsilon\tilde{c}] + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\mu_\epsilon,$$

since by Lemma 2.15, if a condition holds q.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for measures with compact support and finite interaction energy, then the condition also holds a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} &= (1 - \epsilon)c + \epsilon\tilde{c} + (1 - \epsilon) \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\mu_0 + \epsilon \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\nu_0 \\ &= (1 - \epsilon) \left[c + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\mu_0 \right] + \epsilon \left[\tilde{c} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{V}{2} \, d\nu_0 \right] \\ &= (1 - \epsilon)I(\mu_0) + \epsilon I(\nu_0), \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality follows by the definition of c and \tilde{c} . Since I is strictly convex, the above only holds true if, and only if $\mu_0 \equiv \nu_0$, and hence $c = \tilde{c}$, which is as required. \square

Remark 2.20 (Heuristic Idea)

In part (i) of Theorem 2.19, why do we have q.e. on \mathbb{R}^2 ? To have the condition hold on all of \mathbb{R}^2 , for each $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we should be able to choose the measure $\nu = \delta_{x_0}$ in (2.27). But this is not possible since $I(\delta_{x_0}) = \infty$, while we are only allowed to consider measures ν with $I(\nu) < \infty$.

2.2.3 Characterisation of the Minimiser of I

In this subsection, we now proceed to solve the Euler Lagrange conditions obtained in Theorem 2.19 to obtain an explicit expression of the unique minimiser, μ_0 , giving us full insight into the structure of the equilibrium measure.

Theorem 2.21 (Characterisation of the minimiser of I)

The equilibrium measure μ_0 which minimises I is given by $\mu_0 = \frac{1}{\pi}\chi_{B_1(0)}$.

Proof. By Theorem 2.19, the minimiser, μ_0 , of I is uniquely characterised by (EL1) and (EL2). Let $\nu := \frac{1}{\pi}\chi_{B_1(0)}$. We now aim to show that $\mu_0 \equiv \nu$. To show this, we split the proof into two steps.

Step 1: Firstly,

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\nu(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left[\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^1 r^2 r \, dr \, d\theta \right] = \frac{1}{4}.$$

Moreover,

$$\iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x - y| \, d\nu(x) \, d\nu(y) = \frac{1}{4}. \quad (2.29)$$

To prove (2.29), we first show that

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} -\log|x-y| \, dx = -\frac{|y|^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for } y \in B_1(0). \quad (2.30)$$

To determine (2.30), it is useful to work in complex coordinates, so now identify points $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^2$ with points in \mathbb{C} . Then, converting to polar coordinates, that is letting $x = re^{i\theta}$, we find that

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} -\log|x-y| \, dx = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^1 r \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|re^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta \, dr.$$

We are now left to deal with two cases, when $r < |y|$ and $r \geq |y|$. If $r < |y|$, then since $-\log|re^{i\theta} - y|$ is harmonic for $y \in \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus B_r(0)$, by the mean value property for harmonic functions,

$$\int_0^{2\pi} -\log|re^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta = -2\pi \log|y|.$$

If instead, $r > |y|$,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|re^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta &= \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|r - ye^{-i\theta}| \, d\theta \\ &= \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|r - \bar{y}e^{i\theta}| \, d\theta = -2\pi \log r, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality follows again by the the mean value property, where we have interchanged the roles of r and $|y|$. Finally, if $r = |y|$, then for $s \in (0, r)$, $\lim_{s \rightarrow r^-} (-\log|se^{i\theta} - y|) = -\log|re^{i\theta} - y|$ and $-\log|se^{i\theta} - y|$ is integrable with respect to θ and less than or equal to $\log|s|$ for all $s \in (0, r)$. Hence by the dominated convergence theorem

$$\int_0^{2\pi} -\log|re^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta = \lim_{s \rightarrow r^-} \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|se^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta = \lim_{s \rightarrow r^-} -2\pi \log|s| = -2\pi \log r,$$

where the second equality follows by the case when $r < |y|$ and the third equality follows since $|y| = r$. Then for $y \in B_1(0)$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} -\log|x-y| \, dx &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{|y|} r \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|re^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta \, dr + \int_{|y|}^1 r \int_0^{2\pi} -\log|re^{i\theta} - y| \, d\theta \, dr \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi} \left[-\pi|y|^2 + \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi|y|^2 \log|y| - \frac{\pi}{2}|y|^2 \right] \\ &= -\frac{|y|^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

which proves (2.30). Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| \, d\nu(x) \, d\nu(y) &= \frac{1}{\pi^2} \int_{B_1(0)} \int_{B_1(0)} -\log|x-y| \, dx \, dy \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} 1 - |y|^2 \, dy \\ &= \int_0^1 r(1-r^2) \, dr = \frac{1}{4}, \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows by (2.30), and the last equality follows by switching to polar coordinates and letting $y = re^{i\theta}$, which proves the claim. Hence,

$$c_\nu := I(\nu) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\nu(x) = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Step 2: By (2.30) and since $-\log|x|$ is harmonic for $x \in B_1(0)^c$, we have that

$$(W * \nu)(x) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \log|x-y| \, dy = \begin{cases} -\frac{|x|^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} & x \in B_1(0), \\ -\log|x| & x \notin B_1(0). \end{cases} \quad (2.31)$$

Since $c_\nu = \frac{1}{2}$, by (2.31)

$$(W * \nu)(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{|x|^2}{2} + \frac{|x|^2}{2} = \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for } x \in B_1(0),$$

which shows that ν solves (EL2). Now, again by (2.31),

$$(W * \nu)(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} = -\log|x| + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \quad \text{for } x \notin B_1(0).$$

If we let $r = |x|$ and $f(r) := -\log r + \frac{r^2}{2}$ for $r \geq 1$, to show that ν solves (EL1), it suffices to show that $f(r) \geq \frac{1}{2}$ for all $r \geq 1$. Since $f'(r) = -\frac{1}{r} + r$, $f'(r) = 0$ if, and only if $r = 1$, and $f''(r)|_{r=1} = \frac{1}{r^2} + 1|_{r=1} = \frac{3}{2} > 0$, that is f attains its minimum when $r = 1$, which corresponds to $x \in \partial B_1(0)$. This means that for $x \notin B_1(0)$:

$$(W * \nu)(x) + \frac{V(x)}{2} = -\log|x| + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq -\log|y| + \frac{|y|^2}{2} \Big|_{y \in \partial B_1(0)} = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Therefore ν also solves (EL2), and hence since the Euler-Lagrange conditions uniquely characterise the equilibrium measure μ_0 , we must have that $\mu_0 \equiv \nu = \frac{1}{\pi} \chi_{B_1(0)}$. Furthermore, since $\mu_0 \equiv \nu$, $I(\mu_0) = I(\nu) = \frac{3}{4}$. \square

Remark 2.22

The equilibrium measure μ_0 obtained in Theorem 2.21 is commonly known as the *circle law* in Random Matrix Theory. The calculation of equilibrium measure μ_0 shows that for a $N \times N$ matrix whose entries are determined under a Gaussian probability distribution, as $N \rightarrow \infty$ the eigenvalues of the matrix are distributed uniformly, i.e. they are all a uniform constant distance from each another. This is known as the Ginibre ensemble, see [18]. This follows because the distribution of eigenvalues in a random matrix is identical to the distribution of positions of charges of a two dimensional Coulomb gas under the quadratic confinement potential, which was exactly the case considered in this chapter.

2.3 Scaled Confinement Potential

Now we *tune* the confinement term in the interaction energy I , and consider

$$I_\gamma(\mu) := - \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \log|x-y| \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \gamma \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu(x),$$

for $\gamma > 0$ and see the effect of the tuning on the minimiser. By similar arguments that were applied to the classical interaction energy I , the interaction energy I_γ is strictly convex, and there exists a unique minimiser of I_γ which has compact support and finite interaction energy.

Theorem 2.23

The equilibrium measure μ_γ which minimises I_γ is given by $\mu_\gamma := f_\gamma \# \mu_0$, where $f_\gamma(x) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{\gamma}}$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and μ_0 is the equilibrium measure for the interaction energy I .

Proof. Let μ_γ represent the minimiser of I_γ . Then $I_\gamma(\mu_\gamma) = \min_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)} I_\gamma(\mu)$. For any $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, there exists $\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $\mu = f\#\nu$. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} I_\gamma(\mu_\gamma) &= \min_{\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)} \left[- \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \log |x - y| \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \gamma \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu(x) \right] \\ &= \min_{\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)} \left[- \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \log |f(x) - f(y)| \, d\nu(x) \, d\nu(y) + \gamma \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |f(x)|^2 \, d\nu(x) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \log \gamma + \min_{\nu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)} I(\nu) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \log \gamma + I(\mu_0) \\ &= I_\gamma(f\#\mu_0) \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows Proposition 1.45 and fourth equality follows by Theorem 2.21. Then by uniqueness of minimisers of I_γ , we must have that $\mu_\gamma = f\#\mu_0$, as required. \square

Remark 2.24

The choice of $\gamma > 0$ was made a priori, since if $\gamma \leq 0$, then on \mathbb{R}^2 , an equilibrium measure for the interaction energy I_γ does not exist.

If $\gamma \leq 0$, consider $\mu_n := \frac{1}{\pi n^2} \chi_{B_n(0)}$ for some arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}$, which is a probability measure on \mathbb{R}^2 . Then by [9]

$$\begin{aligned} I_0(\mu_n) &= - \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \log |x - y| \, d\mu_n(x) \, d\mu_n(y) + \gamma \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu_n(x) \\ &= \int_{B_n(0)} \frac{1}{2} - \log n - \frac{1}{2n^2} |x|^2 \, dx + \frac{\gamma}{\pi n^2} \int_{B_n(0)} |x|^2 \, dx \\ &= \pi n^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} - \log n \right) + \left(\gamma - \frac{1}{2n^2} \right) \int_{B_n(0)} |x|^2 \, dx. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\gamma \leq 0$, by taking $n \rightarrow \infty$, we find that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_0(\mu_n) = -\infty$. In particular, $\inf I_0 = -\infty$ over $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, and so no equilibrium measure exists. This behaviour can be predicted since if

(i) $\gamma = 0$, there is no confinement term present in the interaction energy, i.e. no energy input as a result of an attractive *force* keeping the particles together and hence in a bounded domain. That is, the repulsive force induced by the logarithm is overpowering and therefore distributing the mass over \mathbb{R}^2 as a whole;

(ii) $\gamma < 0$, then the confinement term present no longer acts as an attractive potential which would fight against the repulsive behaviour of the interaction potential. Instead, it would further act as a repulsive potential, helping speed up the process in which the mass in our domain is spread out over \mathbb{R}^2 .

Chapter 3

Anisotropic Energies

In this chapter, our interest shifts to the study of interaction energies with either an anisotropic confinement potential or an anisotropic interaction potential, where the anisotropy is of a certain kind. We determine that in both cases, unique minimisers for the interaction energies do exist and can be expressed explicitly.

For use throughout the chapter, define by $\Omega(a, b)$, the region within an ellipse with semi-axes $a, b > 0$, i.e.

$$\Omega(a, b) := \left\{ (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \frac{x_1^2}{a^2} + \frac{x_2^2}{b^2} < 1 \right\}. \quad (3.1)$$

We further denote the *eccentricity* of the ellipse $\Omega(a, b)$ by c , i.e. $c^2 = b^2 - a^2$.

We begin this chapter by studying the case of the interaction energy of an anisotropic confinement potential.

3.1 Anisotropic Confinement Potential

In studying interaction potentials of the form (2.1), the confinement potential V , represents the potential of a force that acts on the particles to keep them in a bounded domain. When $V(x) = |x|^2$ as was considered in Chapter 2, the force exerted on the particles is radial and is represented by the vector field $F(x) = -\nabla V(x) = -2x$, as shown in Figure 3.1a). But in

Figure 3.1: Plot of the vector field $F(x) = -\nabla V(x)$ for three different confinement potentials V . For a) $V(x) = |x|^2$, b) $V(x) = 5x_1^2 + x_2^2$ and c) $V(x) = x_1^2 + 5x_2^2$.

a.

the material sciences, the confinement forces, e.g. shearing forces being applied on a piece of metal tend not to act from all direction, and typically only in either the x_1 or the x_2 direction.

As can be seen from Figures 3.1b) and 3.1c), the shearing force behaviour can be mimicked by making the coefficients of the x_1 or x_2 terms very large. Therefore, it is interesting to see how a directional change in the norm in the confinement potential alters the behaviour of the equilibrium minimiser.

Therefore, in this section we consider an anisotropic interaction energy of the following form: for $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ and $\alpha \geq \beta \geq 0$, we define:

$$I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu) := - \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} \log|x-y| \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} (\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2) \, d\mu(x), \quad (3.2)$$

where $x := (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The choice $\alpha \geq \beta$ can be made without loss of generality, since if $\beta \geq \alpha$, then one can perform a $\pi/2$ rotation about the origin to obtain an identical interaction energy with the roles of α and β interchanged. Throughout this section, we shall reserve the definition $W(x) := -\log|x|$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

For the following, the discrete interaction energy corresponding to the mean field energy (3.2) is

$$I_n^{\alpha,\beta}(x_1, \dots, x_n) = -\frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i \neq j} \log|x_i - x_j| + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha x_{i,1}^2 + \beta x_{i,2}^2), \quad (3.3)$$

where $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in (\mathbb{R}^2)^n$ denote the positions of n particles in the plane (i.e. in \mathbb{R}^2), and $x_i = (x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for each $i = 1, \dots, n$. Furthermore, as in Chapter 2, we may view $I_n^{\alpha,\beta}$ as being defined on the space $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of probability measures in \mathbb{R}^2 through the one-to-one correspondence (2.2). Therefore, for any $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, we may define $I_n^{\alpha,\beta}$ as

$$I_n^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu) = \begin{cases} I_n^{\alpha,\beta}(x_1, \dots, x_n) & \text{if } \mu = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}, \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We see that $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ is the general form of (2.1), for $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Since V is bounded below and is continuous for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, the majority of the main results from Chapter 2 will follow directly, or with very minor changes. In particular, Theorem 3.1 follows by Remark 2.4.

Theorem 3.1 (Γ -convergence of $I_n^{\alpha,\beta}$)

The sequence of functionals $(I_n^{\alpha,\beta})_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, with $I_n^{\alpha,\beta} : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ defined in (3.3), Γ -converges to the functional $I^{\alpha,\beta} : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ in (3.2), as $n \rightarrow \infty$, with respect to the weak convergence of measures. Namely,

- (i) for any $\mu, \mu_n \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure, $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu_n) \geq I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu)$;
- (ii) for all $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, there exists a sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu_n) \leq I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu)$.

Theorem 3.2

There exists $\mu_{\alpha,\beta} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu_{\alpha,\beta}) \leq I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu)$ for all $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Furthermore, the minimiser of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ is unique and has compact support.

Sketch Proof. The existence of a minimiser of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ and the fact that minimisers of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ are compactly supported follows as in Theorem 2.6 with very minor alterations. Furthermore, the proof of uniqueness of minimisers of I defined as in 2.4 only made use of the interaction potential W , and since the interaction potential remains unchanged, i.e. $W = -\log|\cdot|$, uniqueness of minimisers of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ follows as before. \square

Then, by the proof of Theorem 2.19, we obtain the Euler-Lagrange conditions for the interaction energy $I^{\alpha,\beta}$.

Theorem 3.3 (Euler-Lagrange Conditions)

The minimiser $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ is uniquely characterised by the following Euler-Lagrange conditions: there exists $c_{\alpha,\beta} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(i) \quad (W * \mu)(x) + \frac{\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2}{2} \geq c_{\alpha,\beta}, \quad \text{for q.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^2; \quad (\text{EL1})$$

$$(ii) \quad (W * \mu)(x) + \frac{\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2}{2} = c_{\alpha,\beta}, \quad \text{for } \mu\text{-a.e. } x \in \text{supp}(\mu). \quad (\text{EL2})$$

In particular,

$$c_{\alpha,\beta} := I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} (\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2) \, d\mu(x).$$

Remark 3.4 (Heuristic Idea on the Equilibrium Measure of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$)

Heuristically, the effect of the anisotropy in the confinement term of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ would be to turn the equilibrium measure in Chapter 2 into an ellipse. Therefore it is natural to expect that the minimising measure of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ would be the characteristic function of an ellipse, $\frac{1}{ab\pi} \chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$, with semi-axes a and b . To check this intuition, we will impose that $\frac{1}{\pi ab} \chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$ satisfies (EL1) and (EL2). We see that (EL2) gives the expression of the semi-axes a, b in terms of α, β , since it states that for all $x \in \Omega(a, b)$, the following must hold

$$\left[\alpha b - \frac{2b}{a(a+b)} \right] x_1^2 + \left[\beta a - \frac{2a}{b(a+b)} \right] x_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) = c_{\alpha,\beta}, \quad (3.4)$$

where $c_{\alpha,\beta}$ is a constant. Therefore, by matching coefficients, for the characteristic measure on the ellipse $\Omega(a, b)$ to satisfy (EL2), the coefficients of x_1^2 and x_2^2 in (3.4) must equal zero and therefore α and β must satisfy the following semi-axis conditions

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{2\beta}{\alpha(\alpha+\beta)}} \quad \text{and} \quad b = \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha}{\beta(\alpha+\beta)}}. \quad (3.5)$$

We note that since $\alpha \geq \beta \geq 0$, it follows that $0 \leq a \leq b$. More precisely, we have the following.

Theorem 3.5 (Characterisation of the minimiser of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$)

The equilibrium measure $\mu_{a,b}$ which minimises $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ in (3.2) is given by $\mu_{a,b} = \frac{1}{ab\pi} \chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$, where $\Omega(a, b)$ is as in (3.1), and $a = \sqrt{\frac{2\beta}{\alpha(\alpha+\beta)}}$ and $b = \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha}{\beta(\alpha+\beta)}}$.

Proof. We show that $\mu_{a,b} = \frac{1}{ab\pi} \chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$ with a, b as above solves both (EL1) and (EL2). By [9, Section 4],

$$W * \mu_{a,b}(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{ab} \frac{bx_1^2 + ax_2^2}{a+b} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } x \in \Omega(a, b), \\ J(x) & \text{if } x \in \Omega(a, b)^c, \end{cases} \quad (3.6)$$

where, by identifying \mathbb{R}^2 as \mathbb{C} by setting $z = x_1 + ix_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$, we may write J as

$$J(z) = \begin{cases} -\log |z| & \text{if } a = b, \\ -\frac{1}{c^2} \Re(z\sqrt{z^2 + c^2} - z^2) - \log |\sqrt{z^2 + c^2} + z| + \log 2 + \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } a < b, \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

where \Re denotes the real part of a complex number and $c = \sqrt{b^2 - a^2}$. For brevity, we define the function $f : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as the left hand side of (EL1) and (EL2), i.e.

$$f(x) := W * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2}{2}.$$

(EL2) Firstly, let $x \in \Omega(a, b)$. Then,

$$W * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2}{2} = \left[\alpha b - \frac{2b}{a(a+b)} \right] x_1^2 + \left[\beta a - \frac{2a}{b(a+b)} \right] x_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right),$$

which is constant only if the coefficients of the x_1^2 and x_2^2 terms are zero, that is when a, b satisfy (3.5). Hence for $\mu_{a,b}$ to be good candidate for the minimiser of $I^{\alpha,\beta}$, a, b must satisfy (3.5), and by Remark 3.4, for such a choice of a, b , it follows that

$$W * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2}{2} = \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right).$$

Therefore to show that $\mu_{a,b}$ solves (EL2), we must also show that

$$c_{\alpha,\beta} := I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu_{a,b}) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2 \, d\mu_{a,b} = \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right). \quad (3.8)$$

To this end, by applying the following change of variables $(x_1, x_2) = (ay_1, by_2)$ and then changing to polar coordinates,

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2 \, d\mu_{a,b}(x) = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Moreover, by (3.6),

$$\begin{aligned} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| \, d\mu_{a,b}(x) \mu_{a,b}(y) &= \frac{1}{ab\pi} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} -\frac{1}{ab} \frac{by_1^2 + ay_2^2}{a+b} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \, dy \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2ab\pi} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \alpha y_1^2 + \beta y_2^2 \, dy \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \alpha y_1^2 + \beta y_2^2 \, d\mu_{a,b}(x). \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} I^{\alpha,\beta}(\mu_{a,b}) &= \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} -\log|x-y| \, d\mu_{a,b}(x) \, d\mu_{a,b}(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2 \, d\mu_{a,b}(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2 \, d\mu_{a,b}(x), \end{aligned}$$

which shows that (3.8) holds true. Therefore, for any $x \in \Omega(a, b)$,

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2} - \log \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) = c_{\alpha,\beta},$$

as required, showing that $\mu_{a,b}$ solves (EL2) when (3.5) holds, as expected from the discussion in Remark 3.4.

(EL1) We now aim to show that for all $x \in \Omega(a, b)^c$ with a, b as in (3.5), $f(x) \geq c_{\alpha,\beta}$ for the constant $c_{\alpha,\beta}$ as in (3.8). This is in fact equivalent to showing that the radial component of the gradient of f is positive outside $\Omega(a, b)$, i.e. for all $x \in \Omega(a, b)^c$

$$\underbrace{x \cdot \nabla W * \mu_{a,b}(x)}_{(\star)} + \underbrace{\alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2}_{(\dagger)} = x \cdot \nabla f(x) \geq 0. \quad (3.9)$$

To show (3.9), it is useful to work in complex coordinates, i.e. by setting $z = x_1 + ix_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ for any $x \in \Omega(a, b)^c$. By (3.6), $W * \mu_{a,b}(x) \equiv J(x)$ for all $x \in \Omega(a, b)^c$, and by [9, Section 4]:

$$\nabla J(x) = 2\partial_{\bar{z}}J(z) = \begin{cases} -\frac{1}{\bar{z}} & \text{if } a = b, \\ -\frac{2}{c^2} \left(\sqrt{\bar{z}^2 + c^2} - \bar{z} \right) & \text{if } a < b, \end{cases}$$

where $\partial_{\bar{z}} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial_{x_1} + i\partial_{x_2})$. The operator $x \cdot \nabla$ is a real valued, and has a complex equivalent of the form $x \cdot \nabla \equiv \Re[2\bar{z}\partial_{\bar{z}}]$. Therefore (\star) is equal to

$$2\Re[\bar{z}\partial_{\bar{z}}J(z)] = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{if } a = b, \\ -\frac{2}{c^2}\Re[\bar{z}\sqrt{\bar{z}^2 + c^2} - \bar{z}^2] & \text{if } a < b. \end{cases}$$

Now rewriting (\dagger) in complex form, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2 &= \Re \left[\alpha \left(\frac{z + \bar{z}}{2} \right)^2 + \beta \left(\frac{z - \bar{z}}{2} \right)^2 \right] \\ &= \Re \left[\frac{(\alpha - \beta)(z^2 + \bar{z}^2) + 2(\alpha + \beta)|z|^2}{4} \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} ((\alpha - \beta)\Re(z^2) + (\alpha + \beta)|z|^2). \end{aligned}$$

We now check (EL1) when $\alpha = \beta$, and when $\alpha > \beta$.

If $\alpha = \beta$, then since $a = \sqrt{\frac{2\beta}{\alpha(\alpha+\beta)}}$ and $b = \sqrt{\frac{2\alpha}{\beta(\alpha+\beta)}}$, it follows that $a = b$, and so

$$x \cdot \nabla f(x) = \alpha|z|^2 - 1 \geq 0 \quad \text{for } z \in \Omega(a, a)^c,$$

since for $z \in \Omega(a, a)^c$, $|z| \geq a = \frac{1}{\alpha}$. Thus $\mu_{a,b}$ solves (EL1) when $\alpha = \beta$.

If $\alpha > \beta$, hence $a < b$, then

$$\begin{aligned} x \cdot \nabla f(x) &= \Re \left[-\frac{2}{c^2} \left(\bar{z}\sqrt{\bar{z}^2 + c^2} - \bar{z}^2 \right) \right] + \frac{1}{2} ((\alpha - \beta)\Re(z^2) + (\alpha + \beta)|z|^2) \\ &= \frac{1}{ab}|z|^2 + \frac{a^2 + b^2}{abc^2}\Re[z^2] - \frac{2}{c^2}\Re[\bar{z}\sqrt{\bar{z}^2 + c^2}], \end{aligned}$$

where we have used that $\alpha = \frac{2}{a(a+b)}$ and $\beta = \frac{2}{b(a+b)}$. To demonstrate (3.9), after multiplying across by abc^2 , it suffices to deduce that for all $z \in \Omega(a, b)^c$

$$2ab\Re[\bar{z}\sqrt{\bar{z}^2 + c^2}] \leq c^2|z|^2 + (a^2 + b^2)\Re[z^2]. \quad (3.10)$$

Now to show (3.10), it is useful to rewrite $z \in \Omega(a, b)$ in a convenient way, that is in terms of an elliptical coordinate system that preserves the foci of the ellipse $\Omega(a, b)$. More precisely, for $z = x_1 + ix_2 \in \Omega(a, b)^c$, we write

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = c \sinh(s) \cos \theta & \theta \in [0, 2\pi), \\ x_2 = c \cosh(s) \sin \theta & s \in [\tanh^{-1}(\frac{a}{b}), \infty). \end{cases}$$

Then any $z = x_1 + ix_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ can be written as $z = c \sinh(s + i\theta)$ for some $\theta \in [0, 2\pi)$ and $s \geq \tanh^{-1}(\frac{a}{b})$. We now rewrite each term of (3.10) in this new elliptical coordinate system as

follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\Re\left[\bar{z}\sqrt{\bar{z}^2+c^2}\right] &= \Re\left[c^2\sinh(s-i\theta)\cosh(s-i\theta)\right] = \frac{c^2}{2}\sinh(2s)\cos(2\theta), \\ |z|^2 &= c^2\sinh(s+i\theta)\sinh(s-i\theta) = \frac{c^2}{2}(\cosh(2s)-\cos(2\theta)), \\ \Re[z^2] &= \Re\left[c^2\sinh^2(s+i\theta)\right] = \frac{c^2}{2}(\cosh(2s)\cos(2\theta)-1).\end{aligned}$$

Hence, for $z \in \Omega(a, b)^c$, $s \geq \tanh^{-1}\left(\frac{a}{b}\right)$, it follows that, in this new elliptical coordinate system, up to a factor of $\frac{1}{2}$, $c^2|z|^2 + (a^2 + b^2)\Re[z^2] - 2ab\Re\left[\bar{z}\sqrt{\bar{z}^2+c^2}\right]$ is equal to

$$\begin{aligned}c^2(\cosh(2s)-\cos(2\theta)) &+ (a^2+b^2)(\cosh(2s)\cos(2\theta)-1) - 2ab\sinh(2s)\cos(2\theta) \\ &= 2\cos(2\theta)(a\cosh(s)-b\sinh(s))^2 + c^2\cosh(2s) - (a^2+b^2) \\ &\geq -2(a\cosh(s)-b\sinh(s))^2 + c^2\cosh(2s) - (a^2+b^2) \\ &\geq 0,\end{aligned}$$

since $s \mapsto c^2\cosh(2s) - 2(a\cosh(s) - b\sinh(s))^2$ is an increasing function, and for $s = \tanh^{-1}\left(\frac{a}{b}\right)$, it equals $(a^2 + b^2)$. Thus, the inequality in (3.10) holds true for all $z \in \Omega(a, b)^c$, which implies that $x \cdot \nabla f(x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in \Omega(a, b)^c$, as required. Therefore $\mu_{a,b}$ also solves (EL1) when $\alpha > \beta$. Hence $\mu_{a,b}$ is the unique minimiser of the interaction energy $I^{\alpha,\beta}$ for a and b as in (3.5). \square

3.2 Anisotropic Interaction Potential

In nature, when *particles* interact with one another, it is very rare for the interaction potential to be radial, that is to act equally in all directions. For example, when considering a crowd of people, the way in which a person within a crowd interacts with their surroundings is typically not only dependent on the distance from the individual, but also on the individual's field of view. That is, we should expect interaction potentials in this situation to have a radial and angular dependence, which would deem it anisotropic. Interaction potentials having angular dependence are not restricted to the situation of a crowd of people, but also applicable to situations involving a flock of birds or traffic, see [14]. In this section we consider an anisotropic potential coming from material science, which describes the interactions among defects in metals [17, 23, 9], in particular, for $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$

$$W_1(x_1, x_2) = -\log|x| + \frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}.$$

When written in polar coordinates, $(x_1, x_2) = (r \cos \theta, r \sin \theta)$, this anisotropic interaction potential, W_1 , becomes

$$W_1(r, \theta) = -\log r + \cos^2 \theta.$$

Note that the potential W_1 , unlike the case of the purely logarithmic interaction potential in Chapter 2, contains an additional term with an angular dependence.

In this section we characterise explicitly the minimiser of an interaction energy with a tuned anisotropic interaction potential described above. We *tune* the anisotropic term in the interaction potential to make it more or less prominent, and then study the way in which the tuning affects certain properties of the equilibrium measure, i.e. the dimensionality of the support, and the distribution of mass of the equilibrium measure. In particular we study an interaction

energy with an anisotropic interaction potential of the following form: for $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ define

$$I^\alpha(\mu) = \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} W_\alpha(x-y) \, d\mu(x) \, d\mu(y) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu(x), \quad (3.11)$$

where $x = (x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and $W_\alpha(x) := -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x^2}{|x|^2}$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

For the following, the discrete interaction energy corresponding to the mean field energy (3.11) is given by

$$I_n^\alpha(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i \neq j} \left(-\log|x_i - x_j| + \alpha \frac{(x_{i,1} - x_{j,1})^2}{|x_i - x_j|^2} \right) + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|^2, \quad (3.12)$$

where $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in (\mathbb{R}^2)^n$ denotes the positions on n particles in the plane. Furthermore, as we have done for the classical logarithmic interaction energy in Chapter 2, and for the interaction energy with an anisotropic confinement potential in Chapter 3, Section 3.1, we may view I_n^α as being defined on the space $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of probability measures in \mathbb{R}^2 through the one-to-one correspondence (2.2). Therefore, for any $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, we may define I_n^α as:

$$I_n^\alpha(\mu) = \begin{cases} I_n^\alpha(x_1, \dots, x_n) & \text{if } \mu = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_{x_i}, \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Once again, a majority of the main results from Chapter 2 that hold for the classical interaction energy I also hold for I^α since the anisotropy $x_1^2/|x|^2$ is lower semicontinuous and bounded below.

Theorem 3.6 (Γ -convergence of I_n^α)

The sequence of functionals $(I_n^\alpha)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, with $I_n^\alpha : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ defined in (3.12), Γ -converges to the functional $I^\alpha : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ in (3.11), as $n \rightarrow \infty$, with respect to the weak convergence of measures. Namely,

- (i) for any $\mu, \mu_n \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure, $\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n^\alpha(\mu_n) \geq I^\alpha(\mu)$;
- (ii) for all $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$, there exists a sequence $(\mu_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subseteq \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $\mu_n \rightharpoonup \mu$ weakly in measure and $\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} I_n^\alpha(\mu_n) \leq I^\alpha(\mu)$.

In this section, we aim to compute the minimiser of I^α . For this, we are first required to prove the existence and uniqueness of the minimiser.

Theorem 3.7

For $\alpha \in (-1, 1)$, there exists $\mu_\alpha \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ such that $I^\alpha(\mu_\alpha) \leq I^\alpha(\mu)$, for I^α as defined in (3.11), for all $\mu \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Furthermore, the minimiser of I^α is unique and has compact support.

Proof. We split this proof into multiple steps.

Step 1 - Existence: Existence of a minimising measure for I^α follows by the proof of existence in Theorem 2.6 and Remark 2.4, since the anisotropy in the interaction potential of I^α is lower semicontinuous and bounded from below.

Step 2 - Uniqueness: To prove uniqueness, we prove that I^α is strictly convex in the spirit of Theorem 2.6. Strict convexity, in turn follows by showing that W_α satisfies a positivity condition of the type of Lemma 2.5, which was shown for W_0 (i.e. $\alpha = 0$). For this, as in Section 2.2.1, it suffices to show that $\widehat{W}_\alpha > 0$ for all Schwartz functions $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\varphi(0) = 0$ and $\varphi > 0$. Note that we only need to compute the Fourier transform of the anisotropic term of W_α , since the Fourier transform of the logarithm was computed in Proposition 2.7.

For the calculation of the Fourier transform of the anisotropic term of W_α , it is useful to rewrite the anisotropy as follows

$$\frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2} = \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{x_1^2 - x_2^2}{|x|^2} \right).$$

Indeed, $P(x) := x_1^2 - x_2^2$ is a homogeneous harmonic polynomial of degree 2, and so by [31, Theorem 5, page 73]

$$\widehat{\frac{x_1^2 - x_2^2}{|x|^2}}(\xi) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{\xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2}{|\xi|^4}.$$

Therefore,

$$\widehat{\frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}}(\xi) = \frac{1}{2} \delta_0(\xi) - \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{\xi_1^2 - \xi_2^2}{|\xi|^4},$$

since the Fourier transform of a constant function is the Dirac delta. Hence, by Proposition 2.7, for $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \widehat{W}_\alpha, \varphi \rangle &= \left(\frac{\alpha}{2} + \gamma + \log \pi \right) \varphi(0) + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{|\xi| \leq 1} \frac{(1-\alpha)\xi_1^2 + (1+\alpha)\xi_2^2}{|\xi|^4} (\varphi(\xi) - \varphi(0)) \, d\xi \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{|\xi| > 1} \frac{(1-\alpha)\xi_1^2 + (1+\alpha)\xi_2^2}{|\xi|^4} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi, \end{aligned}$$

and for $\varphi \in \mathcal{S}$ with $\varphi(0) = 0$ and $\varphi > 0$,

$$\langle \widehat{W}_\alpha, \varphi \rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} \frac{(1-\alpha)\xi_1^2 + (1+\alpha)\xi_2^2}{|\xi|^4} \varphi(\xi) \, d\xi > 0 \quad \forall \alpha \in (-1, 1),$$

as required. \square

As for the classical logarithmic interaction energy, and for the interaction energy with an anisotropic confinement potential, the minimiser of W_α is also characterised by similar Euler-Lagrange conditions, where we replace W in Theorem 2.19 by W_α for $\alpha \in (-1, 1)$. We omit the proof since it is the same as for Theorem 2.19.

Theorem 3.8 (Euler-Lagrange Conditions)

For $\alpha \in (-1, 1)$, the minimiser $\mu_\alpha \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{R}^2)$ of I^α is uniquely characterised by the following Euler-Lagrange conditions: there exists $c_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$(i) \quad (W_\alpha * \mu_\alpha)(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq c_\alpha, \quad \text{for q.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^2; \quad (\text{EL1})$$

$$(ii) \quad (W_\alpha * \mu_\alpha)(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} = c_\alpha, \quad \text{for } \mu_\alpha\text{-a.e. } x \in \text{supp}(\mu_\alpha). \quad (\text{EL2})$$

In particular,

$$c_\alpha := I^\alpha(\mu_\alpha) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 \, d\mu_\alpha(x).$$

Remark 3.9

As in Remark 3.4, we can deduce the necessary conditions for an ellipse, $\frac{1}{\pi ab}\chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$ to be an equilibrium measure of I^α . To determine the necessary conditions, we employ (EL2) of Theorem 3.8. For (EL2) to hold true for the characteristic measure of the ellipse, the following conditions must hold:

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{a(a+b)}\left(1 - \frac{\alpha b}{a+b}\right) &= \frac{1}{2}, \\ \frac{1}{b(a+b)}\left(1 + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}\right) &= \frac{1}{2},\end{aligned}\tag{3.13}$$

which once solved imply that for $\alpha \in (-1, 1)$, we must have that $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$.

Finally, we now characterise the minimiser of I^α .

Theorem 3.10 (Characterisation of the minimiser of I^α)

For $\alpha \in (-1, 1)$, the equilibrium measure of I^α is given by $\mu_\alpha = \frac{1}{\pi ab}\chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$, where $\Omega(a, b)$ is as in (3.1), with $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$.

Proof. It suffices to consider the case when $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ since the case $\alpha = 0$ has already been covered in Chapter 2, and the case $\alpha \in (-1, 0)$ follows by swapping x_1 and x_2 . Let $\mu_{a,b} := \frac{1}{\pi ab}\chi_{\Omega(a,b)}$ for some $0 < a < b$.

(EL2) We first employ (EL2) to determine a and b in terms of α . For $x \in \Omega(a, b)$, by (3.6),

$$-\log|\cdot| * \mu_{a,b}(x) = -\frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \log|x-y| \, dy = -\frac{1}{ab} \frac{bx_1^2 + ax_2^2}{a+b} - \log\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2}.\tag{3.14}$$

Now to determine $W_\alpha * \mu_{a,b}$, we need only to determine $(x_1^2/|x|^2) * \mu_{a,b}$. To this end, we make use of the following trick. If we let $(y_1, y_2) = (av_1, bv_2)$, then the left hand side of (3.14) becomes

$$-\frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \log|x-y| \, dy = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \log((x_1 - av_1)^2 + (x_2 - bv_2)^2) \, dv_1 \, dv_2,$$

and if we evaluate the left hand side (3.15) at $x = (au_1, bu_2)$, we obtain:

$$-\frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \log|x-y| \, dy \Big|_{x=(au_1, bu_2)} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \log(a^2(u_1 - v_1)^2 + b^2(u_2 - v_2)^2) \, dv_1 \, dv_2.\tag{3.15}$$

Now if we denote the axial aspect ratio by $\sqrt{k} = \frac{a}{b}$, using (3.15), we may rewrite the right hand side of (3.14) as

$$-\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \log(k(u_1 - v_1)^2 + (u_2 - v_2)^2) \, dv_1 \, dv_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{k}u_1^2 + u_2^2}{(1 + \sqrt{k})} - \log(1 + \sqrt{k}) + \log 2 + \frac{1}{2}.\tag{3.16}$$

Then differentiating both sides of (3.16) with respect to k and multiplying across by -2 ,

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \frac{(u_1 - v_1)^2}{k(u_1 - v_1)^2 + (u_2 - v_2)^2} \, dv_1 \, dv_2 = \frac{u_1^2 - u_2^2}{\sqrt{k}(1 + \sqrt{k})^2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{k}(1 + \sqrt{k})}.\tag{3.17}$$

Reverting back to the original coordinate system (x, y) , we notice that (3.17) actually represents a scaled version of the convolution of the anisotropic term with $\mu_{a,b}$, since

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \frac{(u_1 - v_1)^2}{k(u_1 - v_1)^2 + (u_2 - v_2)^2} \, dv_1 \, dv_2 = \frac{b^2}{a^2} \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \frac{(x_1 - y_1)^2}{|x - y|^2} \, dy.\tag{3.18}$$

Hence, after multiplying across by $\frac{a^2}{b^2}$ in (3.18), by (3.17), it follows that for $x \in \Omega(a, b)$

$$\left(\frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}\right) * \mu_{a,b}(x) = \frac{a}{a+b} + \frac{bx_1^2 - ax_2^2}{ab(a+b)^2}.$$

Thus for $x \in \Omega(a, b)$,

$$\begin{aligned} W_\alpha * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} &= \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{a(a+b)} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha b}{a+b}\right) \right] x_1^2 + \left[\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{b(a+b)} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}\right) \right] x_2^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} - \log\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}. \end{aligned}$$

For $\mu_{a,b}$ to be a good candidate as a minimiser of I^α , $W_\alpha * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2}$ must be constant on $\Omega(a, b)$, and hence the coefficients of x_1^2 and x_2^2 must vanish. This holds true when a, b satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{a(a+b)} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha b}{a+b}\right) &= \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{b(a+b)} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}\right) &= \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{3.19}$$

Solving (3.19), we find that $\mu_{a,b}$ is a good candidate for a minimiser of I^α only if $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$. This means that if the minimiser is an ellipse of the form $\mu_{a,b}$, then this ellipse has to have semi-axes $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$. Furthermore to show that $\mu_{a,b}$ solves (EL2), we must also show that

$$c_\alpha := I^\alpha(\mu_{a,b}) - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} |x|^2 d\mu_\alpha(x) = \frac{1}{2} - \log\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}, \tag{3.20}$$

for $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$. Now since we may rewrite c_α as

$$\begin{aligned} c_\alpha &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} W_\alpha * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} d\mu(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} W_\alpha * \mu_{a,b}(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} dx, \end{aligned}$$

and since by the choice of a, b , the integrand above is constant for $x \in \Omega(a, b)$, and in particular equal to $\frac{1}{2} - \log\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}$. It then follows that

$$\begin{aligned} c_\alpha &= \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \frac{1}{2} - \log\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - \log\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{\alpha a}{a+b}, \end{aligned}$$

which is as required. Hence $\mu_{a,b}$ solves (EL2) for $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$.

(EL1) Now let

$$\mu_\alpha := \mu_{a,b}|_{a=\sqrt{1-\alpha}, b=\sqrt{1+\alpha}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\alpha^2}} \chi_{\Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})}.$$

Then, to show that μ_α is the minimiser of I^α , we need to show that it also solves (EL1). That is for all $x \in \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})^c$

$$W_\alpha * \mu_\alpha(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq c_\alpha,$$

for the value c_α defined in (3.20). For this, as for the case for an anisotropic confinement potential in Section 3.1, we use the fact that for $z \notin \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})$

$$-\log |\cdot| * \mu_\alpha(z) = J(z),$$

with J defined as in (3.7). Now express $z = x_1 + ix_2 \in \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})^c$ in terms of the following elliptical coordinates which follows the shape of $\Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})$,

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = c \sinh(\xi) \sin \eta & \eta \in [0, 2\pi), \\ x_2 = c \cosh(\xi) \cos \eta & \xi \in [\tanh^{-1}(\frac{a}{b}), \infty). \end{cases}$$

In terms of ξ and η , since $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $0 < a < b$, we have that

$$J(\xi, \eta) = -\xi - \frac{1}{2}e^{-2\xi} \cos(2\eta) - \log \frac{c}{2}.$$

Therefore for any $x \in \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})^c$,

$$-\frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} \log |x-y| dy \Big|_{x=(c \sinh(\xi) \sin \eta, c \cosh(\xi) \cos \eta)} = -\xi - \frac{1}{2}e^{-2\xi} \cos(2\eta) - \log \frac{c}{2}. \quad (3.21)$$

Now, letting $y = (av_1, bv_2)$ we rewrite the left hand side of (3.21) as

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})} \log |x-y| dy \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \log \left(a^2 \left(\frac{x_1}{a} - v_1 \right)^2 + b^2 \left(\frac{x_2}{b} - v_2 \right)^2 \right) dv_1 dv_2 \\ &= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \log \left(k \left(\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{k}} - v_1 \right)^2 + (k+c^2) \left(\frac{x_2}{\sqrt{k+c^2}} - v_2 \right)^2 \right) dv_1 dv_2 \\ &=: f(x; k) \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality follows by letting $a = \sqrt{k}$ and $b = \sqrt{k+c^2}$. Differentiating f with respect to k , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f(x; k)}{\partial k} &= -\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{B_1(0)} \frac{\left(\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{k}} - v_1 \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x_2}{\sqrt{k+c^2}} - v_2 \right)^2}{k \left(\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{k}} - v_1 \right)^2 + (k+c^2) \left(\frac{x_2}{\sqrt{k+c^2}} - v_2 \right)^2} dv_1 dv_2 \\ &\quad + \int_{B_1(0)} \frac{\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{k}} \left(\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{k}} - v_1 \right) + \frac{x_2}{\sqrt{k+c^2}} \left(\frac{x_2}{\sqrt{k+c^2}} - v_2 \right)}{k \left(\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{k}} - v_1 \right)^2 + (k+c^2) \left(\frac{x_2}{\sqrt{k+c^2}} - v_2 \right)^2} dv_1 dv_2 \\ &= -\frac{c^2}{2a^2b^2}g(x) - \frac{1}{2b^2} - \frac{1}{2}\nabla f(x) \cdot \left(\frac{x_1}{a^2}, \frac{x_2}{b^2} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$g(x) = \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})} \frac{(x_1 - y_1)^2}{|x-y|^2} dy. \quad (3.22)$$

But (3.21) shows that the function f is independent of k and so $\frac{\partial f}{\partial k} = 0$. Hence by the derivation of $\frac{\partial f}{\partial k}$ in terms of x calculated above, for any $x \in \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})^c$ we can rewrite g (which is the convolution of the anisotropic term of the interaction potential W_α with μ_α) as

$$g(x) = -\frac{a^2}{c^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \nabla f(x) \cdot (b^2 x_1, a^2 x_2),$$

where $a = \sqrt{1-\alpha}$, $b = \sqrt{1+\alpha}$ and $c = 2\alpha$. Next, to calculate the explicit form for g , we simplify the gradient of f . For this, it is convenient to let $z = \sinh \xi$ and $\rho = \sin \eta$. Then for any $x \in \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})$, we may write

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = cz\rho & z \geq \frac{a}{c}, \\ x_2 = c\sqrt{(1+z^2)(1-\rho^2)} & \rho \in [-1, 1]. \end{cases}$$

Now in these new coordinates, we rewrite f as

$$f(z, \rho) = -\log\left(z + \sqrt{1+z^2}\right) - \frac{1-2\rho^2}{2(z + \sqrt{1+z^2})^2} - \log \frac{c}{2}.$$

Rewriting the gradient operator with respect to this new coordinate system (z, ρ) yields

$$\nabla \equiv \frac{1}{c(z^2 + \rho^2)} \left\{ \left[(1+z^2)\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + z(1-\rho^2) \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right] \mathbf{e}_1 + \sqrt{1+z^2}(1-\rho^2) \left[z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} - \rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right] \mathbf{e}_2 \right\},$$

where \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 denote the canonical basis of \mathbb{R}^2 , and since

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{1+z^2}} + \frac{1-2\rho^2}{\sqrt{1+z^2}(z + \sqrt{1+z^2})^2}, \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial \rho} = \frac{2\rho}{(z + \sqrt{1+z^2})^2},$$

it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla f(x) \cdot (b^2 x_1, a^2 x_2) \Big|_{x=(c\rho z, c\sqrt{(1+z^2)(1-\rho^2)})} &= \nabla f(x) \cdot (b^2 cz\rho, a^2 c\sqrt{(1+z^2)(1-\rho^2)}) \\ &= -\frac{2(a^2(1-\rho^2)\sqrt{1+z^2} + b^2\rho^2 z)}{z + \sqrt{1+z^2}}, \end{aligned}$$

which allows us to write the convolution of the anisotropy of the interaction potential with μ_α as

$$g(z, \rho) = -\frac{a^2}{c^2} + \frac{2(b^2\rho^2 z + a^2(1-\rho^2)\sqrt{1+z^2})}{c^2(z + \sqrt{1+z^2})}.$$

Furthermore, in the new coordinate system, we may write the confinement term as

$$h(z, \rho) := \frac{|x|^2}{2} \Big|_{x=(c\rho z, c\sqrt{(1+z^2)(1-\rho^2)})} = \frac{c^2(1-\rho^2+z^2)}{2}.$$

Given the definitions of f, g and h , we may rewrite the left hand side of (EL1) as

$$W_\alpha * \mu_\alpha(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \Big|_{x=(c\rho z, c\sqrt{(1+z^2)(1-\rho^2)})} = f(z, \rho) + \alpha g(z, \rho) + h(z, \rho), \quad (3.23)$$

and since f, g, h are all functions of the form $A(z)\rho^2 + B(z)$, where A and B are functions of z , different for f, g and h respectively, we may write

$$f(z, \rho) + \alpha g(z, \rho) + h(z, \rho) = C(z)\rho^2 + D(z),$$

which is a quadratic equation in ρ , where C and D are some functions of z . Since $f + \alpha g + h$ is a quadratic in ρ and $\rho \in [-1, 1]$, if the sign of C is positive, then $f + \alpha g + h$ is an increasing function of ρ , and hence achieves its minimum when $\rho = 0$. If instead the sign of C is negative, then $f + \alpha g + h$ is a decreasing function of ρ , and hence achieves its minimum when $\rho = 1$. Therefore to show that $W_\alpha * \mu_\alpha(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq c_\alpha$ for all $x \in \Omega(\sqrt{1-\alpha}, \sqrt{1+\alpha})^c$, it suffices to show

that this is true when $\rho = 0$ and $\rho = 1$ separately.

If $\rho = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} f(z, 0) &= -\log\left(z + \sqrt{1 + z^2}\right) - \frac{1}{2(z + \sqrt{1 + z^2})^2} - \log \frac{c}{2}, \\ g(z, 0) &= -\frac{a^2}{c^2} + \frac{2a^2\sqrt{1 + z^2}}{c^2(z + \sqrt{1 + z^2})}, \\ h(z, 0) &= \frac{c^2(1 + z^2)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z}(f(z, 0) + \alpha g(z, 0) + h(z, 0)) = \frac{c^2 z^2 - a^2}{\sqrt{1 + z^2}} \geq 0,$$

as $z^2 \geq \frac{a^2}{c^2}$, the function $(f + \alpha g + h)(z, 0)$ is an increasing function of z for all $z \geq \frac{a}{c}$, and because

$$(f + \alpha g + h)\left(\frac{a}{c}, 0\right) = c_\alpha,$$

it follows that $(f + \alpha g + h)(z, 0) \geq c_\alpha$ for all $z \geq \frac{a}{c}$.

If $\rho = 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} f(z, 1) &= -\log\left(z + \sqrt{1 + z^2}\right) + \frac{1}{2(z + \sqrt{1 + z^2})^2} - \log \frac{c}{2}, \\ g(z, 1) &= -\frac{a^2}{c^2} + \frac{2b^2 z}{c^2(z + \sqrt{1 + z^2})}, \\ h(z, 1) &= \frac{c^2 z^2}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z}(f(z, 1) + \alpha g(z, 1) + h(z, 1)) = \frac{c^2 z^2 - a^2}{\sqrt{1 + z^2}} \geq 0,$$

as $z^2 \geq \frac{a^2}{c^2}$, the function $(f + \alpha g + h)(z, 1)$ is an increasing function of z for all $z \geq \frac{a}{c}$, and because

$$(f + \alpha g + h)\left(\frac{a}{c}, 1\right) = c_\alpha,$$

it follows that $(f + \alpha g + h)(z, 1) \geq c_\alpha$ for all $z \geq \frac{a}{c}$. Therefore, by (3.23), it follows that for all $x \in \Omega(\sqrt{1 - \alpha}, \sqrt{1 + \alpha})^c$,

$$W_\alpha * \mu_\alpha(x) + \frac{|x|^2}{2} \geq c_\alpha.$$

which shows that for $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, μ_α solves (EL1). Since the Euler-Lagrange conditions of I^α uniquely characterise the minimiser of I^α , for $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, the minimiser of I^α is μ_α as required. \square

3.2.1 Limit Case: $\alpha = 1$

In this subsection we study the limiting behaviour of the minimiser of I^α as $\alpha \rightarrow 1^-$. The full study of the case when $\alpha = 1$ is done in [23].

We have that $I^\alpha \nearrow I^1$ pointwise increasingly as $\alpha \rightarrow 1^-$, and that I^α is lower semicontinuous for each $\alpha \in [0, 1)$, hence by Proposition 1.20, I^1 is also lower semicontinuous and $\Gamma\text{-lim}_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} I^\alpha = I^1$. Since μ_α minimises I^α for each $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $\mu_1 := \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} \mu_\alpha$, where the convergence is in the sense of weak convergence of measures, must then minimise I^1 by Theorem 1.26. It now suffices to compute μ_1 . We find that

$$\mu_1 = \frac{1}{\pi} \delta_0 \otimes \sqrt{2 - x_2^2} \mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner (-\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2}). \quad (3.24)$$

The measure μ_1 in (3.24) is known as the *semi-circle law* in probability theory.

Proof. Let $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be chosen arbitrarily. Then for $a = \sqrt{1 - \alpha}$ and $b = \sqrt{1 + \alpha}$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_\alpha(x) &= \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{\Omega(a,b)} f(x) \, d\mu_\alpha(x) \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{-b}^b \int_{-\frac{a}{b}\sqrt{b^2-x_2^2}}^{\frac{a}{b}\sqrt{b^2-x_2^2}} f(x_1, x_2) \, dx_1 \, dx_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{-b}^b \int_{-1}^1 f\left(\frac{a}{b}\sqrt{b^2-x_2^2}u_1, x_2\right) \frac{a}{b}\sqrt{b^2-x_2^2} \, du_1 \, dx_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi ab} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} \int_{-1}^1 f\left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{2-u_2^2}u_1, \frac{b}{\sqrt{2}}u_2\right) \frac{a}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{2-u_2^2} \frac{b}{\sqrt{2}} \, du_1 \, du_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} \int_{-1}^1 f\left(\frac{a}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{2-u_2^2}u_1, \frac{b}{\sqrt{2}}u_2\right) \sqrt{2-u_2^2} \, du_1 \, du_2, \end{aligned}$$

where the third equality follows by applying the change of variable $x_1 = \frac{a}{b}\sqrt{b^2-x_2^2}u_1$ and the fourth equality follows by applying the change of variables $x_2 = \frac{b}{\sqrt{2}}u_2$. Now passing to the limit as $\alpha \rightarrow 1^-$ and moving the limit inside the integral, which is allowed as $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_\alpha(x) &= \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} \int_{-1}^1 f\left(\sqrt{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}}\sqrt{2-u_2^2}u_1, \sqrt{\frac{1+\alpha}{2}}u_2\right) \sqrt{2-u_2^2} \, du_1 \, du_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} \int_{-1}^1 \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} f\left(\sqrt{\frac{1-\alpha}{2}}\sqrt{2-u_2^2}u_1, \sqrt{\frac{1+\alpha}{2}}u_2\right) \sqrt{2-u_2^2} \, du_1 \, du_2 \end{aligned}$$

and because f is continuous on \mathbb{R}^2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} \int_{-1}^1 f(0, u_2) \sqrt{2-u_2^2} \, du_1 \, du_2 \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} f(0, u_2) \sqrt{2-u_2^2} \sqrt{2} \, du_2. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_1(x) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \sqrt{2-x_2^2} \, d\delta_0(x_1) \, d\mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner (-\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2})(u_2) \\ &= \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\sqrt{2}}^{\sqrt{2}} f(0, x_2) \sqrt{2-x_2^2} \, dx_2, \end{aligned}$$

it follows that

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_\alpha(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_1(x). \quad (3.25)$$

Since $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ was chosen arbitrarily, (3.25) holds for all $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$, and hence μ_α converges weakly to μ_1 in the sense of measures as $\alpha \rightarrow 1^-$, as required. \square

Similarly, one finds that as $\alpha \rightarrow -1$, the minimising measure of I^{-1} is given by:

$$\mu_{-1} = \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{2 - x_1^2} \mathcal{L}^1 \llcorner (-\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{2}) \otimes \delta_0.$$

3.3 Numerics

In this section we study, through the use of MATLAB, the discrete interaction energy I_n given by

$$I_n(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \frac{1}{n^2} \sum_{i \neq j} W(x_i - x_j) + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V(x_i),$$

where $(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in (\mathbb{R}^2)^n$ denotes the positions of n particles in the plane, and n is large. In particular, we plot and study the minimising distribution the particles (x_1, \dots, x_n) take under various different interaction potentials W and confinement potentials V .

The MATLAB Program: The MATLAB program, that approximates the distribution a system of particles take to minimise the discrete interaction energy I_n , works under the Euler method. To determine the minimiser of I_n , the program solves the system of equations $\partial_{x_i} I_n = 0$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Since, for each $i = 1, \dots, n$

$$\partial_{x_i} I_n = 0 \quad \iff \quad \frac{1}{n} \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n \nabla W(x_i - x_j) + \nabla V(x_i) = 0,$$

to specify the interaction and the confinement potentials for a computation, for each $i = 1, \dots, n$, we input the explicit expressions for ∇W and ∇V as a vector of the $\partial_{x_{i,1}}$ and the $\partial_{x_{i,2}}$ terms. Then under the initial condition of a uniform distribution, z_0 , the program iteratively computes

$$z_0 = z_0 - \epsilon \left(\sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n \nabla W(x_i - x_j) + \nabla V(x_i) \right),$$

where $\epsilon = e-4$. After 5000 iterations, we output a scatter plot of z_0 , which displays an approximate minimising distribution of I_n .

3.3.1 $W(x) = -\log|x| + \alpha \left(\frac{x^2}{|x|^2}\right)^p$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$ with $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}, p \geq 2$

Figure 3.2: Plots of the distribution of particles under the interaction energy I_n when $W(x-y) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x^2}{|x|^2}$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$, for various values of α . For a) $\alpha = -1$, b) $\alpha = -0.75$, c) $\alpha = -0.5$, d) $\alpha = -0.25$, e) $\alpha = 0$, f) $\alpha = 0.25$, g) $\alpha = 0.5$, h) $\alpha = 0.75$, i) $\alpha = 1$.

We notice that in Figure 3.2, the equilibrium measure μ_α , obtained for the mean field energy I^α in Chapter 3, Section 3.2, clearly well approximates the minimising distribution of I_n^α for n large. Furthermore, we observe the loss dimensionality in the support μ_α as $|\alpha| \rightarrow 1^-$, which was predicted.

Figure 3.3: Plots of the support of the equilibrium measures for I_n when $W(x-y) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x^4}{|x|^4}$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$, for various values of α . For a) $\alpha = -1$, b) $\alpha = -0.75$, c) $\alpha = -0.2$, d) $\alpha = 0.5$, e) $\alpha = 1$, f) $\alpha = 4/3$.

Figure 3.4: Plots of the support of the equilibrium measures for I_n when $W(x-y) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x^6}{|x|^6}$ and $V(x) = |x|^2$, for various values of α . For a) $\alpha = -1$, b) $\alpha = -0.5$, c) $\alpha = -0.1$, d) $\alpha = 0.6$, e) $\alpha = 1.2$, f) $\alpha = 1.6$.

3.3.2 $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2$

Figure 3.5: Plots of the distribution of particles under the interaction energy I_n when $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = \alpha x_1^2 + \beta x_2^2$, with α, β taking various values. For a) $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1$ b) $\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 1$ c) $\alpha = 1.5, \beta = 1$ d) $\alpha = 1, \beta = 0.5$ e) $\alpha = 1, \beta = 1.5$ f) $\alpha = 5, \beta = 5$.

3.3.3 $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = |x|^p$ with $p \geq 2$

Figure 3.6: Plots of the distribution of particles under the interaction energy I_n with $W(x) = -\log|x|$ and $V(x) = |x|^p$ where p takes various values. For a) $p = 4$, b) $p = 8$ and c) $p = 12$.

3.3.4 $W(x) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}$ and $V(x) = \beta x_1^2 + \gamma x_2^2$, with $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}$

Figure 3.7: Plots of the distribution of particles under the interaction energy I_n with $W(x) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}$ and $V(x) = \beta x_1^2 + \gamma x_2^2$, where α, β, γ take various values. For a) $\alpha = -1, \beta = 3, \gamma = 1.5$, b) $\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.9, \gamma = 0.8$ and c) $\alpha = 1.1, \beta = 1, \gamma = 4$.

3.3.5 $W(x) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}$ and $V(x) = |x|^p$

Figure 3.8: Plots of the distribution of particles under the interaction energy I_n with $W(x) = -\log|x| + \alpha \frac{x_1^2}{|x|^2}$ and $V(x) = |x|^p$, where α and p take various values. For a) $\alpha = 1, p = 4$, b) $\alpha = 1, p = 8$ and c) $\alpha = 1, p = 12$, d) $\alpha = -0.25, p = 20$, e) $\alpha = 0.7, p = 14$, f) $\alpha = -1, p = 6$.

Appendix A

Chapter 1

A.1 Topology

Definition A.1 (Basis of a Topology)

Let (X, τ) be a topological space. A *basis* for the topology τ is a collection \mathcal{B} of subsets of τ such that every $U \in \tau$ is the union of some collection of sets in \mathcal{B} .

Definition A.2 (Local Basis)

Let (X, τ) be a topological space and let $x \in X$. A *local basis* of x is a collection of open neighbourhoods of x , \mathcal{B}_x , such that for all $U \in \tau$, with $x \in U$, there exists a set $B \in \mathcal{B}_x$ such that $x \in B \subseteq U$.

Definition A.3 (First Countable)

Let (X, τ) be a topological space. Then (X, τ) is said to be a *first countable* topological space if every point $x \in X$ has a countable local basis.

Proposition A.4

Every metric space is first countable.

Proof. If we consider the metric space \mathbb{R}^n under the usual topology, then the claim follows by noticing that the collection:

$$\mathcal{B}_x = \left\{ B_{\frac{1}{n}}(x) \mid n \in \mathbb{N} \right\},$$

forms a countable local basis for any $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The proof is similar to a general metric space. \square

A.2 Measure Theory

Definition A.5 (Measure)

Let (X, Σ) be a measure space, then:

- (i) We say that $\mu : \Sigma \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is a *real measure* if $\mu(\emptyset) = 0$, and for any sequence $(A_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of pairwise disjoint elements of Σ :

$$\mu \left(\bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \mu(A_n).$$

- (ii) If μ is a measure, we define its *total variation* $|\mu|$ for every $E \in \Sigma$ as:

$$|\mu|(E) := \sup \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\mu(E_n)| \mid E_n \in \mathcal{M} \text{ pairwise disjoint, } E = \bigcup_{n=1}^{\infty} E_n \right\}.$$

(iii) If μ is a real measure, the *positive* and *negative* parts of μ are defined respectively as:

$$\mu^+ := \frac{|\mu| + \mu}{2}, \quad \mu^- := \frac{|\mu| - \mu}{2}.$$

Theorem A.6 (See [1, Theorem 1.6])

Let (X, Σ, μ) be a measure space. Then, $|\mu|$ is a positive finite measure.

Remark A.7

Theorem A.6 states that for any measure μ on a measurable space (X, Σ) , the total variation $|\mu|$ is also a measure, and thus the positive and negative parts of μ are positive finite measures. Therefore, a decomposition of μ of the form $\mu = \mu^+ - \mu^-$ makes sense.

Remark A.8

The total variation measure in fact forms a norm on the space of measure \mathcal{M} . In fact \mathcal{M} is also a Banach space.

Definition A.9 (Borel)

Let X be metric space and let \mathcal{B} be its Borel σ -algebra and consider the measure space (X, \mathcal{B}) . A positive measure, $\mu : \mathcal{B} \rightarrow [0, \infty]$, on (X, \mathcal{B}) is called a Borel measure.

Definition A.10 (Product σ -algebra)

Let Σ and Λ be σ -algebras. We define the product σ -algebra as the set:

$$\Sigma \otimes \Lambda := \sigma(\{A \times B \mid A \in \Sigma, B \in \Lambda\}).$$

A.2.1 Important Results

Theorem A.11 (Monotone Convergence Theorem)

Let $f, f_n : X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ for $n \in \mathbb{N}$ be a sequence of measurable functions, and suppose that $f_n \nearrow f$ μ -almost everywhere. Then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_X f_n \, d\mu = \int_X f \, d\mu.$$

Theorem A.12 (Dominated Convergence Theorem)

Suppose that $f_n : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are measurable, and $f_n \rightarrow f$ almost everywhere. If there exists $g : X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$, such that g is integrable and $|f_n| \leq g$ pointwise $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$, then f is integrable and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_X f_n \, d\mu = \int_X f \, d\mu.$$

Theorem A.13 (Fatou's Lemma)

Let $f_n : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a sequence of measurable functions. Then

$$\int_X \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f_n(x) \, d\mu(x) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_X f_n(x) \, d\mu(x).$$

Theorem A.14 (Fubini)

Let μ and ν be σ -finite measures and let $f : X \times Y \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be $\Sigma \otimes \Lambda$ -measurable, and $\phi := \mu \otimes \nu$. Now, if either of the following is true

(i) $f \geq 0$ pointwise (Tonelli's Theorem), or

(ii) $f \in L^1(\phi)$,

then,

$$\int_{X \times Y} f \, d\phi = \int_X \left(\int_Y f(x, y) \, d\nu(y) \right) d\mu(x) = \int_Y \left(\int_X f(x, y) \, d\mu(x) \right) d\nu(y).$$

Appendix B

Chapter 2

Lemma B.1

For μ^h and μ as in the proof of Theorem 2.3, $\mu^h \rightarrow \mu$ in the sense of measures as $h \rightarrow 0$.

Proof. Let $f \in C_b(\mathbb{R}^2)$ be a test function. Then we may write

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu^h(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \frac{\mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h)}{h^2} \int_{Q_k^h} f(x) \, dx = \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \int_{Q_k^h} f(x) \, dx,$$

and

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \int_{\tilde{Q}_k^h} f(x) \, d\mu(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \int_{\tilde{Q}_k^h} f(x) \, d\mu(x).$$

Then it follows that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_h(x) - \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \left[\int_{Q_k^h} f(x) \, dx - \int_{\tilde{Q}_k^h} f(x) \, d\mu(x) \right]. \quad (\star)$$

Now let x_k^h denote the centre of both Q_k^h and \tilde{Q}_k^h , then

$$\begin{aligned} (\star) &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \left[\int_{Q_k^h} (f(x) - f(x_k^h)) \, dx + f(x_k^h) - f(x_k^h) - \int_{\tilde{Q}_k^h} (f(x) - f(x_k^h)) \, d\mu(x) \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \left[\int_{Q_k^h} (f(x) - f(x_k^h)) \, dx - \int_{\tilde{Q}_k^h} (f(x) - f(x_k^h)) \, d\mu(x) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Note that $\sum_{k=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) = 1 = \mu(\mathbb{R}^2)$. Then for each $k = 1, \dots, N_h$, since f is continuous we have that for any $x \in Q_k^h$ or $x \in \tilde{Q}_k^h$, $f(x) - f(x_k^h) = O(1)$ as $h \rightarrow 0$ uniformly. Therefore,

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \mu(\tilde{Q}_k^h) \left[\int_{Q_k^h} (f(x) - f(x_k^h)) \, dx - \int_{\tilde{Q}_k^h} (f(x) - f(x_k^h)) \, d\mu(x) \right] \leq O(1)$$

as $h \rightarrow 0$ and hence

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu_h(x) - \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} f(x) \, d\mu(x) \right| = 0,$$

which is as claimed. □

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